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Sustainable bio-based construction: A review of MICP technology and bio-cementation across scales and materials

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ABSTRACT

The urgent need to minimize construction-related CO₂ emissions and negative environmental impacts to enhance sustainability and economic circularity in the construction sector has led to revolutionary innovations in traditional practices. During the past two decades, microbially induced calcium carbonate precipitation (MICP), an emerging biomineralization technique mediated by bacteria and photosynthetic algae, has emerged as a widely employed bio-based approach in geotechnical and concrete engineering to treat different types of soils, rocks, as well as grout and concrete. A vast amount of research has been carried out to understand the impact of MICP on the behavior of materials and performance of systems in various contexts. However, most reviews focus individually on the geotechnical aspect (e.g., soil properties) or concrete engineering (e.g., self-healing concrete). This review examines recent developments in the application of MICP to treat diverse materials like soils, rocks, and concrete. The comparative analysis demonstrates that MICP can yield significant engineering improvements, such as increasing the unconfined compressive strength (UCS) of loose sands by up to 1.5–3.0 MPa, restoring up to 386 kPa of splitting tensile strength in cracked mortar, and reducing the permeability of fractured rocks by 3 to 4 orders of magnitude. Additionally, quantitative assessments reveal that optimal reagent concentrations (typically ranging from 0.5 M to 1.0 M of urea and calcium sources) play a major role in maximizing precipitation efficiency across these materials. The review also emphasizes that long-term environmental conditions critically affect the durability of bio-cemented structures. While MICP-treated materials exhibit strong resistance to freeze-thaw cycles (retaining 70%–90% of their initial strength after 12 cycles), wet-dry cycles and acid rain exposure can cause up to an 80% reduction in UCS. The inclusion of bio-additives, such as 0.2–0.4% by weight of basalt or jute fibers, has emerged as a vital strategy, reducing weathering-induced mass loss to 10% and enhancing long-term resilience. This study aims to offer a robust foundation for future research aimed at overcoming existing limitations and scaling MICP technologies for commercial implementation in geotechnical and construction engineering.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Background and fundamental mechanisms of MICP

One of the major thrust areas of geotechnical engineering has always been ground improvement to achieve sufficient bearing resistance while keeping the settlements in the allowable range. Generally, soil improvement refers to the process of treating the soil to maintain, alter, or improve its performance as a construction material. Various ground improvement methods have been used in the literature to improve ground conditions for safe and reliable construction as well as to overcome the problem of the non-availability of suitable construction materials. Based on the treatment method, the engineering techniques of soil improvement can be broadly grouped into three categories: mechanical, biological, and chemical stabilization [1].

Mechanical stabilization is the most common and oldest technique of ground improvement. Its concept is associated with increasing soil density by applying mechanical pressure to compact the shallow layers by static and dynamic loading. In chemical stabilization, various chemically active materials are mixed with soil to improve its properties. Among the most commonly used compounds are inorganic pozzolanic/cementitious binders, such as fly ash, cement, lime, and some calcium-based chemicals, which can also effectively be combined with fibers and geotextile to enhance soil's mechanical and dynamic properties [2–6]. However, the use of chemical stabilizers has caused some environmental concerns, such as increasing CO₂ emissions and having a large carbon footprint, the potential for variation in soil pH, and also the risk of soil and groundwater contamination by the chemical agents or the process byproducts [7].

The concept of soil biological stabilization combines engineering practices with ecological principles, where a bio-mediated method is applied to improve the chemical and mechanical soil behavior. To achieve sustainable solutions, the Microbially Induced Calcium Carbonate Precipitation (MICP) method has emerged as a novel bio-based approach in the realm of soil improvement without the use of cement or industrial agents. The MICP method represents a promising frontier in geotechnical engineering, offering eco-friendly and cost-effective avenues to address various geotechnical challenges, from erodible slopes and foundation support to environmental and construction aspects associated with soft ground conditions.

Currently, there are several known microbial mineralizing bacteria, such as urease-producing bacteria, sulfate-reducing bacteria, denitrifying bacteria, and oxidizing bacteria. Among those bacteria, urease-producing bacteria have been extensively researched and applied due to their low cost, easy extraction and cultivation, good mineralization and cementation effects, and relatively simple reaction process [8]. The key part of the enzymatic hydrolysis process of urea is the catalytic effect of urease produced by specific bacterial strains, such as *Bacillus* and *Sporosarcina pasteurii*. Urea hydrolysis is the process through which urease-producing bacteria convert urea into calcium carbonate. The mechanism of MICP through the urea hydrolysis process can be expressed as follows [9]:

After the bacteria synthesize urease enzyme, urea permeates the bacterial cell, and the urea (CO(NH₂)₂) undergoes hydrolysis, resulting in the generation of ammonia (NH₃) and bicarbonate anions (HCO₃⁻), as depicted in Eqs. (1) and (3). Equilibrium reactions between ammonia and water produce hydroxide ions (OH⁻) (Eq. (2)). The pH on the bacterial surface increases owing to the formation of hydroxide ions, and finally, the supply of calcium ions (Ca²⁺) prompts the precipitation of calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) on the bacterial cell surface, as illustrated in Eq. (4).

Early studies in geomicrobiology from the 1960s to the 1980s documented biologically driven calcium carbonate formation by ureolytic and sulfate-reducing microorganisms in natural marine and sedimentary environments [10,11]. The idea of harnessing this biomineralization process for engineering applications emerged several decades later, with Whiffin's seminal work [12] demonstrating that *Sporosarcina pasteurii* could induce substantial calcite precipitation within sand columns. Subsequent advances by van Paassen et al. [13] included the first large-scale biogrouting demonstration involving treatment of a 100 m³ sand volume, establishing MICP as a practical ground-improvement method. In parallel, DeJong et al. [8,14] provided the first systematic mechanical characterization of MICP-treated soils, showing improvements in stiffness, shear strength, and liquefaction resistance. These foundational studies transformed MICP from a microbiological phenomenon into a geotechnical engineering technique with broad potential for soil stabilization, liquefaction mitigation, erosion control, and rock fracture sealing.

Fig. 1 shows the schematic representation of bacteria cells inducing the formation of calcite crystals via ureolysis [15]. In particular, CaCO₃ crystals formed at inter-particle contacts (circled by red line) contribute directly to bio-cementation, whereas crystals coating particle surfaces (circled by blue line) or suspended in pore spaces (circled by yellow line) may still enhance soil behavior through surface roughening and densification. Although these latter effects are generally less effective than direct cementation in improving peak strength, they may still contribute to the overall response of the treated material. With the interparticle bonding enhancement effect, the MICP technology has been utilized for filling and repairing cracks in stone materials and concrete materials, preventing building leakage, reducing the incidence of sandy soil liquefaction, managing the leakage of containers, preventing soil erosion of sand/soil slope, sand dike erosion, piping, and other defects [16–18]. In comparison to traditional physical/chemical soil modification technologies, MICP is more efficient in modifying rock and soil properties. This method has a relatively simple implementation, with minimal ecological footprint and less environmental impact on the surrounding soil and water [19]. Also, it has a lower viscosity than traditional chemical slurries, making it easier to infiltrate rock and soil materials [20], and it can be used for large-scale treatment of rock and soil [21].

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of bio-chemical reaction network in ureolysis-driven MICP; CaCO_3 crystals at soil inter-particle contacts (circled by red line); CaCO_3 crystals coating soil particles (circled by blue line); CaCO_3 crystals suspended in soil pores (circled by yellow line) [15].

1.2. Photosynthetic microorganisms

Photosynthetic microorganisms, particularly microalgae and cyanobacteria, are increasingly recognized as viable contributors to next-generation, sustainable bio-based building materials. Their potential extends beyond biomineralization to include carbon capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS) and the development of low-carbon construction systems. Recent studies have also explored their integration with MICP-based mineralization processes to enhance both carbon retention and material strength [22]. In addition, bio-derived materials from these systems may support circular economy objectives and reduce embodied emissions when produced sustainably [23–25]. However, important challenges remain, especially regarding long-term durability, biosafety and containment, manufacturing scalability, and regulatory frameworks [26–28]. Compared with the more established bacteria-mediated MICP approaches discussed in this review, these systems are still at an infancy stage of development and are therefore presented here as a future research outlook rather than a central theme of the manuscript.

1.3. Scope and objectives

Focusing on bacterial species, this paper provides a systematic review of the application of the MICP technique, extending from fundamental material improvement (e.g., soil, rock, and concrete) to the broader interdisciplinary perspectives of environmental engineering and CCUS. While the majority of existing review papers have focused primarily on classifying the effects of MICP treatment on the geotechnical properties of soils, or on the biological factors that dictate the process (such as microbial species, solution molarity, and system pH), a critical gap remains in synthesizing how these mechanisms translate across different materials and scales. To address this gap and clearly distinguish from previous literature, this study presents a comparative analysis that highlights novel aspects governing the efficiency of the MICP method across the following dimensions:

- **Material type:** Granular soils, cohesive soils, cementitious materials, and rock.
- **Injection strategies:** Direct injection, premixing, and percolation or surface treatment.
- **Treatment scale:** Spanning from microscopic evidence to macroscopic structural behavior (element tests), meso-scale experiments, and large-scale or field-scale applications.
- **Durability and long-term performance:** Resistance to wetting–drying, freeze–thaw cycles, dissolution, and harsh environmental exposure.

In addition to these core dimensions, the review critically examines the limitations, future opportunities, and practical challenges associated with scaling MICP for engineering practice, paying particular attention to its environmental performance and CO₂-related benefits. Through the identification of key microbial pathways, envisioned field applications, and representative experimental findings, this paper seeks to provide a comprehensive and highly structured understanding of the potential and boundaries of MICP across diverse construction and geotechnical contexts.

2. Application of MICP to different types of materials

2.1. Granular soils

The application of MICP technology to granular materials such as sand has revealed significant promise in the potential enhancement of the characteristics of granular media with minimal environmental impacts. Many researchers have used the unconfined compressive strength (UCS) test to determine the strength of so-called biocemented sands [29,30]. Chu et al. [19] studied the strength of bio-mediated sands using urease-producing microorganisms. The results demonstrated a significant strength increase, as the microbial precipitation of calcium carbonate successfully bonded the loose sand matrix and produced an elevated compressive strength. In another study, Chu et al. [31] discovered a linear relationship between the amount of calcium carbonate precipitation and the unconfined compressive strength of sand specimens treated with MICP. Previous studies have shown that the addition of fiber reinforcement leads to significant improvement in the shear strength and ductility of fiber-reinforced soils [32–34]. In this context, Li et al. [35] examined the influence of randomly distributed discrete fiber addition on the mechanical properties of MICP-treated sand, considering the potential of fibers to increase the shear strength and ductility of the treated material. They conducted unconfined compression tests and triaxial shear strength tests on MICP-treated sands prepared with different percentages (0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, and 0.4%) of fiber. As anticipated, adding fibers significantly enhanced the mechanical properties of MICP-treated sand. Under unconfined compression, the fiber addition led to substantial increases in failure strain (233%), unconfined compressive strength (240%), and elastic modulus (130%). Similarly, under triaxial compression, the fiber-reinforced sand demonstrated notable improvements in failure strain (270%), failure shear strength (253%), elastic modulus (131%), cohesion (311%), and friction angle (51%). Furthermore, the optimum fiber content in MICP-treated sand was found to be 0.2–0.3%.

The cementation effect of MICP on sand at different saturation levels was investigated by Cheng et al. [36] through a series of laboratory experiments, including sieve analysis, permeability, unconfined compressive strength, consolidated undrained triaxial, and durability tests. It was found that lower saturation levels result in higher soil strength for a similar CaCO₃ content. Fig. 2 presents compiled literature data on the relationship between CaCO₃ content and UCS of MICP-treated sand from various studies [9,13,29,36–44], which provides insight into how MICP enhances biochemical reactions and increases soil strength. It is crucial to emphasize that this compilation indiscriminately pools data from highly diverse experimental conditions, including varying initial saturation levels, different sand types, and distinct injection protocols. Because these critical variables are not normalized or stratified, this figure serves purely to illustrate the overarching phenomenological trend that increased CaCO₃ content enhances soil strength, rather than to establish a universal predictive envelope or allow for direct quantitative comparisons across studies.

The permeability of sand is an important geotechnical parameter used to describe fluid flow. Permeability reduction is a process used to make materials less porous, thereby controlling the flow of liquids or gases through them. The MICP technique is one of the potential methods to achieve this objective by clogging the pores of the soil matrix. In the literature, MICP treatment has been mainly applied to sandy soils with relatively high permeabilities [45,46]. Based on permeability tests, Yasuhara et al. [47] examined the hydrodynamic properties of enzymatically induced carbonate precipitation on treated sand samples. Compared with untreated soils, the permeability of improved samples (4×10^{-4} m/s) decreased monotonically by 60%–70% for all cases. Wen et al. [48] explored a new multiple-treatment approach to enhance the immersing method for the MICP treatment of sandy soils. The results indicated that the permeability was reduced from 1.4×10^{-3} m/s to 1×10^{-5} m/s after four treatment injections. More recently, Chen et al. [49] carried out one-dimensional sand column experiments to assess the permeability of MICP-treated calcareous sands. The results revealed that the effective values for cement solution concentration, relative density, and consolidation frequencies range from 0.5 mol/L to 1.5 mol/L, 30%–70%, and 5–15 times, respectively, while the injection–restoration frequency has the greatest effect on permeability.

Data compiled from the literature [36,50–52] are depicted in Fig. 3, demonstrating the correlation between calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) content and permeability. The general trend is that permeability decreases as the CaCO₃ content increases. It should be noted that in Fig. 3, the points are widely scattered, and for the same calcium carbonate content, there are large differences in the degree of permeability reduction. This can be attributed to the initial pore characteristics of the soil and precipitation patterns of CaCO₃ in the pore spaces resulting from different treatment protocols [53].

Overall, the reviewed studies indicate that the improvement of granular soils by MICP cannot be interpreted on the basis of CaCO₃ content alone. Although the general trend is that strength increases and permeability decreases with increasing carbonate

Fig. 2. Relationships between the unconfined compressive strength and the calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) contents [9,13,29,36–44].

Fig. 3. Normalized permeability as a function of calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) content [36,50–52].
Source: Modified from [53].

precipitation, the efficiency of this improvement depends strongly on the location and form of the precipitates within the soil skeleton. At similar CaCO₃ contents, lower saturation levels may produce higher strength because the retained pore solution is concentrated at interparticle contacts in meniscus form, which promotes more effective calcite precipitation at grain-contact bridges rather than less efficient deposition on grain surfaces or within pore spaces [36]. Similarly, the wider scatter observed in permeability-related results suggests that pore clogging is highly sensitive to initial pore geometry, precipitation pattern, and treatment protocol.

Recent studies also show that particle-scale characteristics play a central role. Smaller particle sizes may lead to higher CaCO₃ retention, stronger pore-throat blocking, and greater increases in UCS, whereas larger particles provide more void space in which crystals may grow without forming equally effective load-bearing bonds [54]. However, particle size alone is not sufficient to explain the response, since particle morphology, surface characteristics, and initial density also affect cementation efficiency. A further implication is that similar carbonate contents may correspond to different strength gains depending on whether the precipitates

mainly create effective contact bonds or less efficient deposits within the pore space. This interpretation is also consistent with recent work showing that carbonate content alone does not provide a universal basis for cross-comparison, and that dry density, contact condition, and soil-specific fabric must also be considered [55]. Therefore, in granular soils, the most meaningful interpretation of MICP performance should be based on the combined effect of carbonate amount, precipitation efficiency, soil fabric, and treatment conditions, rather than on carbonate content alone.

2.2. Cohesive soils

According to the literature, research on soil improvement by MICP has focused mainly on granular and, more specifically, sandy soils. However, there is still a lack of research on problematic soils encountered in various regions around the world, such as silty and clayey soils with varying plasticity characteristics [56,57]. The scarcity of research in this field can be attributed to the small scale of pores in clay soils (i.e., micropores) that prevents bacteria from passing freely, and the higher clay content that reduces permeability, making treatment solutions percolate slower and harder [8]. Beyond these transport limitations, the reinforcement mechanisms in cohesive soils also differ from those in granular soils. Instead of forming extensive grain-to-grain calcite bridges along open pore networks, MICP in clays more commonly promotes Ca^{2+} -induced flocculation and aggregation, localized CaCO_3 bonding at inter-aggregate contacts, and partial pore filling within microcracks and fine pores. As a result, the treatment response is highly sensitive to clay mineralogy, initial water content, and solution chemistry, which together control the uniformity of precipitation and the resulting mechanical improvement [58–60]. However, there is a paradox that MICP is more effective in soils containing higher clay contents due to the presence of higher bacterial populations within the clay fraction, which makes this topic appealing for further research. There are some challenges in applying the MICP method for clayey soils. A serious difficulty in tackling soils with high clay contents is their potential to develop desiccation cracks, which degrade the mechanical and hydraulic properties and negatively affect the long-term performance of engineered clay barriers [61].

In this regard, Liu et al. [62] studied the effect of MICP on the remediation of desiccation cracking in clayey soils by performing a series of laboratory desiccation tests on soil samples sprayed with four different fluids: water, bacteria solution, cementation solution, and both bacteria and cement solutions. Under wetting–drying cycles, soil samples treated with MICP showed the least number of cracks on their surfaces, indicating higher resistance to cracking. Moreover, quantification of the relationship between the geometric parameters of crack patterns and MICP treatment cycles demonstrated the merit of the MICP method in decreasing crack width and ratio. In another study, to address the challenges of using MICP for strengthening soft clay, Xiao et al. [57] directly mixed a solution containing *Sporosarcina pasteurii* bacteria, nutrient salts, and soft clay. This approach considerably improved the uniformity of the spatial distribution of the bacteria and nutrients in the soft clay, promoting the formation of calcium carbonate. The results demonstrated that MICP can effectively increase the strength of soft clay, with the unconfined compressive strength increased by a factor of 2.42. Fig. 4 shows the content of calcium carbonate relative to the unconfined compressive strength and the corresponding reduction in water content upon MICP treatment in this study. It is observed that the sample with the highest unconfined compressive strength of 43 kPa has the lowest content of CaCO_3 but the highest reduction in water content (from 40% to about 30%). This indicates that water consumption by the MICP reactions in soft clay is proportional to the increase in the clay's strength, and that the reduction in water content plays a prominent role in enhancing the strength of soft clay.

In many cohesive soils, the strength improvement is often associated with an increase in cohesion (c), while the impact on the internal friction angle (ϕ) varies depending on the soil fabric [60]. For example, the study on reservoir cohesive soils shows that cohesion can increase by over 95%, potentially due to the cementation effect of calcium carbonate crystals generated in the gaps between soil particles, thereby increasing cohesion [63]. However, some expansive soils also exhibit a marked improvement in the internal friction angle, as the precipitation of angular crystals increases the surface roughness and interlocking force of the particles. Accordingly, Tian et al. [64] study confirmed this enhancement, reporting that the cohesion increased from 29.52 to 39.41 kPa and the internal friction angle from 20.13° to 29.58° , indicating a 33.5% gain in cohesion and a 46.9% increase in friction angle, with the stress–strain relationship following a hyperbolic relationship characterized by strain hardening. In natural clays, Arpajirakul et al. [58] showed that the efficiency of calcite precipitation depends strongly on the urea– Ca^{2+} input rate and on soil plasticity, since highly plastic clays hinder liquid transport and reduce treatment uniformity. It was revealed that the small-strain stiffness moduli and UCS values improved by 177 and 278% in the three studied clay types when a urea– Ca^{2+} input rate of 7.5 mmol/h was chosen to induce optimal media clogging, corresponding to the measured calcite content of 18.50%. More recently, an investigation by Maston et al. [59] on kaolin P300 demonstrated that clay saturation state and solution chemistry are also critical, with the highest strength gains obtained at 1.4 M with calcium acetate as the most favorable calcium source for that clay. This was similar to the findings reported by Ghalandarzadeh et al. [65], concluding that the nanoparticle-enhanced biocementation in kaolinite strongly depends on the degree of saturation of the treated samples. At 30% target water content, the MICP + 1.5% nano- SiO_2 treatment increased UCS to about 6 times that of untreated soil and about 15 times that of MICP-treated soil. In another study, Wang et al. [66] proposed a novel biochar-assisted MICP-BIN method for coastal clay reinforcement, using *Sporosarcina pasteurii*. They found that the optimal curing time was about 7 days, reporting that the strength of the MICP-BIN method was superior, reflected in notable increases in the shear strength, internal friction angle, and cohesion, with about 30% more CaCO_3 generated than traditional MICP. Additionally, this method was successful in modifying the soil–water characteristic response, indicating that MICP in clays affects not only strength but also suction and water-retention behavior. Taken together, these studies show that MICP treatment of cohesive soils is feasible, but its performance depends much more strongly than in sands on mineralogy, moisture condition, reagent delivery, and the spatial uniformity of precipitation.

Fig. 4. Variation in unconfined compressive strength and corresponding water reduction of MICP-treated clay samples with CaCO₃ content [57].

2.3. Cementitious materials

Concrete is one of the most widely used man-made materials with high compressive strength and relatively low cost that has been employed in construction [67]. However, it has some drawbacks, such as limited tensile strength and the potential of multi-scaled crack formation upon mechanical, hydraulic and temperature loadings. To overcome these shortcomings, the MICP technique can be exploited for various applications specific to concrete technology, including self-healing, improving durability, mitigating carbon dioxide, and enhancing the strength of concrete.

2.3.1. Crack healing

It is well known that cracks adversely affect the durability of structures [68,69]. Cracks develop in concrete due to several factors, such as compressive and tensile loads, shrinkage, and temperature variations [70]. Cracks serve as open pathways for fluid particles like sulfates, alkalis, and water, which can penetrate and cause steel bar corrosion, leading to concrete deterioration. Traditional crack repair methods use materials such as silicon-based polymers and epoxy systems, which are costly and may degrade over time or harm the environment [71]. Compared to conventional crack repair methods, biomineralization produces fewer harmful byproducts, reducing pollution and promoting green practices. As an advantage, the microorganism can also be activated under external stimuli, allowing mineralization to repair cracks in a structure [72]. The engineering applications of MICP in the field of concrete crack repair are developed in terms of self-healing concrete and the repair of existing concrete cracks by MICP.

To fully acknowledge the impact of MICP in cementitious materials, it is essential to distinguish between the inherent self-healing capacity of traditional concrete and engineered biological interventions. Table 1 presents a comparative analysis of autogenous healing and autonomous (bacterial) healing. While autogenous healing relies on the delayed hydration of unreacted cement particles and natural carbonation, its efficacy is generally restricted to micro-cracks under strict environmental conditions. In contrast, autonomous healing via MICP actively utilizes encapsulated microorganisms to precipitate calcium carbonate, significantly expanding the healable crack width and enhancing long-term durability.

Self-healing is a mechanism where cracks are treated independently without the aid of any additive or external intervention. It is an effective way to minimize the cost of repair and rehabilitation, thereby extending structural life and durability. Self-healing techniques are categorized as either autogenous or autonomous [73,76]. Autogenous healing is a self-healing phenomenon that can occur naturally in cementitious systems with the presence of water upon hydration of unhydrated cement particles [77,78]. On the other hand, the autonomous self-healing process uses different agents and mechanisms, which onset as cracks appear in concrete or smart materials are activated. As autonomous healing relies on embedded unconventional engineering additions rather than unhydrated cement grains, it has the potential to repair larger cracks [79,80].

Various techniques have been used for autonomous self-healing, including encapsulating adhesives and chemicals [81–83], mineral admixtures, and expansive agents [84,85]. However, in the last decade, using bacteria as a self-healing agent has shown high potential, where the bacteria and other relevant agents are inoculated into the concrete matrix during casting. Fig. 5 depicts the scheme of encapsulated bacteria used in self-healing concrete [86]. As a new material for a capsule to protect the bacteria against dry and harsh environments in concrete, Zamani et al. [87] used a polyurea polymer for *Bacillus pseudofirmus* to produce

Table 1
Comparison between autogenous and autonomous healing in cementitious materials [73–75].

Aspect	Autogenous healing (cement hydration)	Autonomous healing (bacterial)
Definition	Intrinsic crack healing by the cementitious matrix itself	Induced by an intentionally introduced healing system
Main Mechanism	Continued hydration and carbonation	Healing triggered by an engineered agent, such as bacteria-mediated CaCO_3 precipitation
External healing agent	Not required	Required
Typical trigger	Moisture and continued reaction of remaining cementitious phases	Moisture, bacterial activation, nutrient supply, and calcium source
Crack-width effectiveness	Generally limited to narrower cracks	Can extend to wider cracks depending on system design

Fig. 5. Concept of interior application of calcium carbonate precipitation-capable bacteria to self-healing concrete.
Source: Based on conceptual framework proposed by Lee and Park [86].

calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) crystals. A major advantage of the polyurea polymer over other self-healing carriers is its fast-curing time, adjustable brittleness, and water insensitivity. They concluded that once the capsule ruptured, the shielded bacteria germinated and were able to consume the available nutrients to precipitate the calcium carbonate necessary to heal the cracks.

The progress of self-healing by mixing bacteria in fresh concrete is satisfactory. Nevertheless, this self-healing method was found to be efficient in cracks smaller than 1 mm, and the repairing effect is limited in larger cracks [88]. This limitation highlights the potential of MICP technology, which has shown promise in repairing pre-existing and larger cracks due to its ability to precipitate calcium carbonate within the cracks, thereby enhancing structural integrity and extending the service life of the concrete [89,90].

Although compressive strength regain and permeability reduction have often been used to measure improvement efficiency, the tensile strength regained after MICP treatment is also a critical indicator, as concrete always cracks under tension. To fill this gap, Choi et al. [91] treated cylinder mortar samples with pre-existing cracks of average widths ranging from 0.15 to 1.64 mm. After 21 cycles of MICP solution treatment, the samples exhibited tensile strengths ranging from 32 to 386 kPa. The MICP-treated samples also showed a reduction in permeability and an increase in tensile strength with an increase in CaCO_3 precipitation on the crack surfaces.

The permeability of the untreated cracked samples varied from 9.24×10^{-6} m/s to 3.03×10^{-3} m/s, corresponding to an average crack width of 0.15 to 1.64 mm. However, after 21 cycles of MICP treatment, the permeability of these samples reduced to a range of 9.0×10^{-7} m/s to 9.65×10^{-6} m/s, approximately three orders of magnitude lower than before MICP repair.

Unlike several studies with qualitative assessment approaches, few researchers applied theoretical methods to quantitatively measure the efficiency of the MICP technique. For instance, Sun et al. [88] developed a theoretical model to address the transport of solutes, suspended biomass, biofilm growth, geochemistry, ureolysis, and precipitation of calcium carbonate (CaCO_3). Their model indicated that suspended biomass concentrations in cracks gradually decreased during the tests, while the larger cracks gained higher concentrations. This theoretical observation was justified by a series of MICP crack repair tests.

Table 2 summarizes key studies on MICP-based crack healing, emphasizing the role of different bacteria, encapsulation techniques, and crack sizes in achieving self-healing and enhanced structural integrity.

Table 2

Overview of selected key studies on MICP-based crack healing, highlighting different bacteria and encapsulation methods, crack sizes, and key outcomes related to the self-healing and remediation of concrete cracks.

Reference	Study focus	Bacteria/Agents	Crack width (mm)	Healing depth (mm)	Healing/Encap. type	Main outcome
Luo et al. [92]	Depth/width of crack healing	Spore-forming alkali-resistant	0.1–1	N/A - Surface build-up cracks	MICP	Better healing in smaller cracks (up to 0.8 mm of width); low crack healing after 60 days
Wang et al. [93]	Spores healing efficiency	<i>Bacillus sphaericus</i>	Up to 0.5	N/A	Hydrogel encaps.	68% permeability reduction; 0.5 mm max crack width healed
Ersan et al. [94]	Performance of MICP with biogranules	Non-axenic ACDC granules	0.4	~10	MICP	80% permeability reduction over 28 days
Zamani et al. [87]	Polyurea encapsulation to protect bacteria	<i>Bacillus pseudofirmus</i>	N/A	N/A - Surface build-up cracks	Polyurea polymer	Polyurea protects bacteria in harsh conditions; successful CaCO ₃ precipitation
Ramachandran et al. [95]	Remediation of synthetic cracks	<i>Bacillus pasteurii</i>	3.175	3.175 and 9.525	MICP with Urea–CaCl ₂	Increase in compressive strength in treated cracks
Achal et al. [96]	Durability properties and remediation of cracks	<i>Bacillus sp.</i>	3	13–27	MICP with Urea–CaCl ₂	50% porosity reduction; compressive strength raised up to 40%; reduced chloride permeability
Choi et al. [91]	Tensile strength recovery	<i>Sp. pasteurii</i>	0.15–1.64	1–2	MICP with Urea–CaCl ₂	Increased tensile strength; reduced permeability after 21 cycles of treatment

2.3.2. Strength and durability improvement

In the frame of strength and durability of uncracked concrete, the MICP technique has shown significant potentials in improving the mechanical characteristics and enhancing the sustainability of concrete. Concerning the concrete properties, Ghosh et al. [97] applied thermophilic anaerobic microorganisms with different concentrations in concrete, and cured at different ages, which showed a 25% improvement in compressive strength. Siddique et al. [98] studied the behavior of rice husk ash bacterial concrete and highlighted the positive impact of bacterial cells on the strength and durability properties of concrete. The best performance was demonstrated by 10% rice husk ash (RHA) addition to concrete, which had a 28-day compressive strength of 36.1 MPa, and the inclusion of the bacterium *Bacillus aerius* (10^5 cells/mL) resulted in a strength of 40.0 MPa.

Kumari et al. [99] conducted a laboratory study to investigate the effect of nonureolytic bacteria (genus *Bacillus*), referring to its merit over ureolytic bacteria that release ammonia during the biomineralization process. Results showed the superior performance of nonureolytic bacteria over ureolytic bacteria. Mondal and Ghosh [100] investigated the influence of bacterial concentration on the compressive strength of treated concrete and found that the maximum compressive strength occurred with a bacterial concentration of 10^5 cells/mL, while a higher concentration of 10^7 cells/mL was more efficient for crack healing.

Hosseini Balam et al. [101] explored the use of *Sporosarcina pasteurii* bacteria to improve the durability of structural concrete members with lightweight aggregates (LWAs) or normal-weight aggregates (NWAs), where seawater was used as a source of calcium in the curing process. Experimental results revealed that the inclusion of bacteria in the concrete mix water led to acceptable results in a seawater medium for both types of concrete tested. This is reflected in a 4% reduction in water absorption and a 26% increase in strength properties, showing the potential of seawater to be used for the enhancement of concrete properties.

Contrary to the evidence presented in much of the literature to date suggesting that MICP enhances concrete strength, Skevi et al. [102] rejected MICP as the main mechanism behind strength improvement in bacterial concrete, questioning the contribution of live and dead *Bacillus cohnii* cells in cement mortar. The results demonstrated that bacteria can enhance the compressive and flexural strength of cement-based materials even when nutrients are unavailable for growth and survival. The primary mechanism for strength enhancement in bacteria-treated cementitious materials was attributed to chemical interactions between bacterial cells and dissolved ions in the cement clinker, as well as the role of bacteria as nucleation sites. However, this must not be confused with the utilization of bacteria for strength improvement and self-healing in cement-based materials. Several conditions must be met to ensure MICP occurs in self-healing concrete, including bacterial viability and nutrient availability. In other words, a distinction must be drawn between the utilization of bacteria for autonomous self-healing (which necessitates active microbial metabolism and nutrient availability to facilitate MICP) and the inherent mechanical reinforcement provided by the presence of bacterial biomass within the cementitious matrix.

Fig. 6a shows the compressive strength values of concrete and mortar specimens reported in the literature [97,99,103,104] versus curing days with different cell concentrations. In general, the reported compressive strength tends to increase with increasing curing time and bacterial cell concentration. However, these improvements should not be attributed uncritically to MICP alone. As highlighted by Skevi et al. [102], strength enhancement in bacterial cementitious materials may also arise from alternative mechanisms, including bacteria–cement chemical interactions and the role of bacterial cells as bio-nucleators for secondary hydration

Fig. 6. (a) Variation in the compressive strength [97,99,103,104] and (b) Comparison of percentage increase in compressive strength of concrete and mortar specimens with different cell concentrations versus curing time reported in various literature [97,99,103,104].

phases. Therefore, while MICP is widely associated with crack healing and durability-related effects, the mechanism governing strength improvement in uncracked cementitious materials remains under discussion. Fig. 6b depicts the percentage increase in compressive strength of the specimens previously discussed in Fig. 6a.

The compressive strength of concrete and a comparison of the percentage increase at 7 and 28 days reported in the literature in terms of the mortar mix, type of bacteria, and cell concentrations are presented in Tables 3 and 4, respectively. To facilitate a clear comparison of how specific mixture parameters influence the efficacy of MICP in cementitious materials, Tables 3 and 4 compile UCS data from various studies. In these tables, the data are grouped by individual references and material types to highlight parametric

Table 3

Compressive strength of concrete and mortar specimens at 7 and 28 days [97,99,103,104].

Parameter	Compressive strength (MPa) (7d/28d)					
	Ghosh et al. [97]	Kumari et al. [99]	Sahoo et al. [104]	Nain et al. [103]		
Cement:Sand ratio	1:3	1:6	1:6	N/A		
Type of bacteria	<i>B. pasteurii</i>	<i>B. cohnii</i>	<i>B. sphaericus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>B. megaterium</i>	Consortia
Untreated (Control)	12.6/23.1	3.9/6.1	29.1/38.2	21.8/38.1		
10 ⁵ CFU/mL	14.7/29.0	4.3/7.7	30.1/43.1	–	–	–
10 ⁶ CFU/mL	13.8/26.6	5.3/8.1	33.6/46.7	–	–	–
10 ⁷ CFU/mL	–	6.2/6.2	38.9/51.9	–	–	–
10 ⁸ CFU/mL	–	–	34.6/45.6	31.9/43.6	27.6/46.7	34.7/44.1

Note: Values are formatted as “7-day strength/28-day strength”. CFU/mL = Colony Forming Units per milliliter. B. = Bacillus.

Table 4

Percentage increase in compressive strength of concrete and mortar specimens at 7 and 28 days [97,99,103,104].

Parameter	Percentage increase (%) (7d/28d)					
	Ghosh et al. [97]	Kumari et al. [99]	Sahoo et al. [104]	Nain et al. [103]		
Cement:Sand ratio	1:3	1:6	1:6	N/A		
Type of bacteria	<i>B. pasteurii</i>	<i>B. cohnii</i>	<i>B. sphaericus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>B. megaterium</i>	Consortia
10 ⁵ CFU/mL	16.7/25.3	11.1/26.2	3.7/12.8	–	–	–
10 ⁶ CFU/mL	9.5/14.7	37.0/32.8	15.6/22.2	–	–	–
10 ⁷ CFU/mL	–	59.8/49.2	33.7/35.9	–	–	–
10 ⁸ CFU/mL	–	–	19.2/27.0	46.4/14.4	26.5/22.6	58.9/15.9

Note: Values are formatted as “7-day increase/28-day increase”. CFU/mL = Colony Forming Units per milliliter. B. = Bacillus.

variations. The first column specifies the primary variable investigated in each study, such as the cement-to-sand ratio or the bacterial cell concentration (measured in CFU/mL). Furthermore, to evaluate the strength development over time, the compressive strength results are presented in an “X/Y” format, representing the 7-day and 28-day curing strengths, respectively.

2.3.3. Carbon dioxide sequestration

Carbon dioxide (CO₂) is a significant greenhouse gas, representing the largest portion of greenhouse emissions. According to the National Ready Mixed Concrete Association, the production of 1 kg of cement releases 0.9 kg of CO₂ [105]. The MICP technique not only aids in crack healing and enhancing mechanical properties but also captures CO₂ before it enters the atmosphere, converting it to carbonate minerals such as calcite, magnesite, and dolomite [106]. This process, known as carbon sequestration or “carbon trap”, captures CO₂ and stores it as carbonate, thereby reducing atmospheric CO₂ levels [107].

Kaur et al. [106] investigated the effect of utilizing CO₂ by *Bacillus megaterium* as an alternative to urea in ureolysis by using CO₂ influx (20 mL/min) as an alternative to urea in carbonate production, yielding CaCO₃ similar to that produced from 2% urea solutions. In carbonation curing, CO₂ reacts with cement products to create calcium carbonate crystals, which increase strength and improve moisture transport and resistance to sulfate and alkali aggregates. As a result of accelerated carbonation curing, concrete strength increased by 117%, whereas the increase in urea-treated specimens was measured to be about 47%.

Meng et al. [108] reviewed the potential of carbonation technologies (including pre-carbonation and accelerated carbonation) and their roles in refining concrete’s microstructure. It was revealed that appropriate carbonation curing could effectively improve concrete’s mechanical properties and refine its microstructure, contrary to weathering carbonation. Also, in terms of the carbon sequestration capacity of Portland cement-based mixes, concentrated and pressurized carbonation achieved the highest CO₂ sequestration (up to 37.2%). Fig. 7 illustrates the typical carbon sequestration in Portland cement-based materials.

While the ability of MICP to capture atmospheric CO₂ and convert it into stable carbonate minerals is a significant advantage for CCUS, its total environmental impact must be evaluated through a life cycle assessment. Recent quantitative analyses revealed that the current practice of MICP has a substantial carbon footprint due to the high energy consumption required to produce its primary inputs. Specifically, the production of urea and calcium chloride (CaCl₂) accounts for 80.4% of the total carbon emissions associated with the MICP process. Under complete reaction conditions, MICP technology needs 0.64 tonnes of urea and 1.08 tonnes of calcium chloride to produce 1 tonne of CaCO₃, and the carbon emission is 2.74 tonnes [109]. Consequently, it is crucial to prioritize low-carbon pathways to keep the MICP potential as a sustainable technology. These could be the transition to industrial-scale applications to reduce unit consumption, the utilization of diversified raw materials such as animal waste or eggshells to replace industrial reagents, and the exploitation of alternative metabolic pathways, such as carbonic anhydrase mineralization, which directly catalyzes the hydration of CO₂ without relying on high-footprint urea.

Despite the potential, very few studies have addressed CO₂ sequestration via MICP in concrete. Using MICP to sequester CO₂ from the direct atmosphere is an excellent option for different types of concrete using a variety of materials, as well as its improved performance and crack-repair process. Thus, it is recommended that a detailed experimental investigation be undertaken on the use of atmospheric CO₂ in MICP for concrete structures while taking into account performance in field applications and implementing several parameters and factors.

Fig. 7. Typical procedures of carbonation curing in cement-based mixes [108].

2.3.4. Offshore infrastructure and oil remediation

MICP technology demonstrates significant potential and visible application prospects in marine engineering, particularly for reinforcing ground and infrastructure [110]. Marine concrete is extensively employed in the construction of marine infrastructure, such as cross-sea bridges, ports, and submerged tunnels [111]. However, concrete structures in marine environments are susceptible to cracking due to prolonged exposure to factors such as seawater erosion, temperature fluctuations, and mechanical loading. MICP, functioning as a bio-cementation method, is therefore utilized to improve the engineering properties of geomaterials in ocean environments [112].

MICP is applied to enhance the engineering behavior of marine sands and foundation soils used in offshore and coastal infrastructure. MICP has been employed to stabilize foundations for offshore installations against erosion [113] and to provide scour protection around monopile foundations [110]. Large-scale field tests have confirmed the efficacy of MICP in reinforcing calcareous foundations on reclaimed coral reef islands [112]. Laboratory and field experiments on MICP-treated calcareous sand demonstrate notable improvements in resistance to erosive processes common in marine environments, including wet-dry cycles, temperature variations, and salt spraying. Although MICP-treated calcareous sand exhibits relatively poorer resistance under actual marine exposure conditions (tides, wave impact, and salinity), the treated specimens maintained structural integrity after 30 days of testing, indicating practical potential for island and coastal infrastructure reinforcement [110].

MICP-based techniques are also deployed for self-healing concrete and environmental mitigation in marine settings. Research has increasingly focused on applying MICP for repairing microcracks in marine concrete [111]. Although factors such as high salinity, ionic interference, and low temperatures may inhibit microbial growth and mineralization, bacteria are still capable of metabolizing calcium carbonate under such conditions. Self-healing systems—often employing encapsulated bacteria (with coral sand used as a potential carrier) and additives such as basalt fibers—have demonstrated effective crack closure in seawater environments [114]. In self-healing mortars incubated in artificial seawater, crack sealing can be accelerated due to a continuous and sufficient supply of calcium ions. Healing products include not only calcite generated by microbial metabolism but also secondary minerals such as aragonite, brucite, and ettringite (Aft), influenced by ions such as Mg^{2+} and SO_4^{2-} in seawater. These additional minerals contribute to crack filling and partial recovery of mechanical performance [111].

MICP technology has also been applied to oil well remediation and environmental protection in marine and offshore settings. Field-scale demonstrations show that *Sporosarcina pasteurii* can be used to enhance wellbore cement integrity under high-pressure and high-temperature conditions [113]. In parallel, MICP has been employed as an environmentally friendly method for fabricating materials used in oil-water separation [115]. This involves coating stainless steel meshes with biologically precipitated calcium carbonate to achieve underwater superoleophobicity (underwater oil contact angle exceeding 151°). Such MICP-coated meshes exhibit extremely high oil intrusion pressure (>3.0 kPa) and oil rejection rates exceeding 99.9%, providing a cost-effective solution for oily wastewater treatment and offering potential utility for mitigating oil spill hazards [115].

2.4. Rock

MICP demonstrates significant potential for stabilizing weathered rocks, which are characterized by reduced cohesion and structural integrity due to environmental exposure. This can lead to slope failure, landslides, seepage issues, and even risk people's lives. By applying MICP, weathered rocks gain increased cohesion through the bio-cementation process, which can mitigate these risks. Fig. 8 illustrates how MICP treatment strengthens weathered rock by sealing fractures through microbial calcium carbonate precipitation, providing the transition from open flow in untreated fractures to reduced permeability with bio-cementation [116].

In particular, microbial grouting can be used to prevent rockfalls located at the tops of slopes, thereby enhancing structural integrity (Fig. 9a). An added benefit of this approach is the formation of anti-erosion layers. These layers offer resistance against weathering forces and minimize slope collapse risks caused by environmental degradation [61]. To avoid secondary sliding in the

Fig. 8. (a) Folded Old Red Sandstone weathered rock formation at St Ann's Head in Pembrokeshire, Wales; (b) schematic of the MICP healing mechanism on rough fractures, illustrating: (i) bacterial attachment to convex surfaces at low flow rates, (ii) formation of narrow necks and gas bubbles, and (iii) unhealed and fully filled fracture areas along the fracture length; (c) grayscale images and macro-healing features of the precipitated calcium carbonate on the two types of fracture surface; (d) typical microscope photos of precipitated calcium carbonates on fracture surfaces [116].

Fig. 9. Application of MICP treatment for preventing and controlling geological disasters [61].

event of landslides (Fig. 9b), microbial grouting may be designed to strengthen the sliding surface, weak structural surfaces, and other potential sliding surfaces. In this case, the MICP technology coupled with spraying technology would be appropriate for treating the slope surface.

As a result of the treatment, a protective layer of dense CaCO₃ is formed on the slope surface to hinder weakening of rock upon rainfall infiltration. To study the spatial distribution of biogrouting in a rock fracture and its effect on permeability reduction, Wu

Fig. 10. The spatial distribution of relative permeability versus displacement for three different types of flows: (I) Surface flow, (II) Transit type, and (III) Channel flow [117].

et al. [117] carried out a series of experiments together with 3D scanning and 3D flow simulation on rock fractures with various initial apertures treated by bio-grouting. It was revealed that the spatial distribution of MICP precipitates in the rock fracture leads to a non-uniform reduction in permeability along the flow direction. This non-uniform reduction in permeability creates distinct zones within the fracture: a rapidly decreasing zone (zone A), a rapidly increasing zone (zone B), and a gradually increasing zone (zone C), which is shown in Fig. 10. The reduction in permeability is influenced by the filling ratio of MICP precipitates, and the flow type transitions from surface flow to channel flow as the fracture aperture decreases below a critical value. The MICP technology is also a promising method to mitigate debris flows. According to Fig. 9c, microbial grouting strengthens loose debris in the source area, enhances its resistance to rainfall erosion, and reduces debris flow risk during the forming period. Similarly, using MICP technology to cement local clastic materials and building a barrier dam in the valley can help retain sediment and reduce debris flows [61].

Table 5 presents a comprehensive summary of various case studies and experimental findings on MICP treatment, focusing on its impact on reducing permeability and enhancing the mechanical properties of fractured rocks across different conditions and treatment parameters.

There is an abundance of investigations focused on the mechanical behavior of rock masses based on DEM [124–128]. Numerical investigations and case studies also show that the main cause of rock mass destabilization and degradation is the progressive failure of rock bridges between joints [129–131]. Consequently, it appears that numerical modeling of rock fractures treated with MICP will be necessary to determine how the MICP technique bonds cracks and joints in natural rocks and weathered rocks.

Accordingly, Cuthbert et al. [132] examined the influence of the MICP technique on reducing fractured rock permeability in the subsurface by combining the results of field experiments with a novel numerical model. For the experimental tests, boreholes with 100 mm diameter were drilled to approximately 27 m depth into a fractured dacite formation, and bacterial injection was conducted to promote calcite precipitation. Modeling was also carried out using COMSOL Multiphysics (v. 4.2a), which simulated the field data by coupling flow, bacterial transport, and solute reactive transport processes. The results demonstrated that MICP can be successfully manipulated under field conditions to reduce the permeability of fractured rock formations. Furthermore, the model was able to reproduce observed data successfully by including feedback mechanisms due to calcite precipitation and by successfully calibrating various parameters, indicating that it accurately captured the complex interactions inherent to MICP.

Despite extensive computational research on self-healing concrete through microbial calcium carbonate precipitation [88,133–135], there remains a lack of investigation into the modeling of weathered rocks treated with the MICP method. As the demand for sustainable geotechnical solutions continues to grow, MICP has emerged as a promising and actively researched approach. Its application in weathered rocks showcases the method's potential to transform challenging geological conditions into opportunities for environmentally friendly and cost-effective engineering solutions. With ongoing advancements and research in this field, the future holds great promise for MICP as a key player in reshaping the landscape of geotechnical engineering.

3. Numerical modeling and multiphysics analysis of MICP processes

Numerical modeling serves as a critical bridge between laboratory observations and field-scale implementation, allowing for the isolation of biochemical and mechanical variables that are difficult to decouple experimentally. Current modeling frameworks are generally categorized into continuum-based multiphysics models and micro-mechanical discrete element method (DEM) simulations.

Table 5
Summary of MICP treatment effectiveness on fractured rock permeability and mechanical properties.

Reference	Objective	Fracture aperture/Matrix type	Treatment duration	Permeability reduction ratio	Key findings
Matsubara [118]	Bio-protection on limestone surfaces by photoautotrophic microorganisms	N/A (weathered limestone surface)	3-hour lab tests; 2017–2019 field study	Qualitative surface stabilization	Reduction in weathering; improved cohesion through biofilm-induced CaCO_3 growth with optimum ~100 ppm of calcium ion concentration
Bucci et al. [119]	Permeability reduction in fractures using triaxial app	N/A (artificially fractured core; 1.5'' in diameter and 3'' in length)	48 h total (two 24-hour reactionary periods)	~80%	Reduced gas/fluid migration in low-permeability formations.
Peng et al. [120]	Assessment of urea and calcium chloride concentration, fracture roughness, and aperture on permeability reduction	1.0 mm to 2.5 mm	~6 days (including saturation and drying phases); 8 injection doses	4 orders of magnitude (reduction to $3 - 5 \times 10^{-5}$ m/s)	Increased treatment efficiency with increasing fracture roughness, urea, and calcium chloride concentrations and decreasing fracture aperture
Song et al. [121]	Mechanical improvement of sandstone	Matrix sealing (Berea sandstone core, no discrete fracture aperture)	10 injection cycles	~96% to ~99% (matrix permeability reduction)	Low-strength/higher permeability sandstone shows 229% UCS, 179% Young's modulus, and 177% brittleness increase; high-strength/lower permeability sandstone shows limited improvement.
Minto et al. [122]	Grouting fine aperture rock fractures	276 μm to 334 μm	3 to 12 days	3 orders of magnitude reduction in transmissivity	Hydraulic aperture reduced significantly, demonstrating effective fracture sealing; controlled calcium carbonate precipitation prevented injection well clogging.
Minto et al. [123]	Permeability control in subsurface engineering works using medical X-ray CT scanner	Matrix sealing (Berea sandstone core, no discrete fracture aperture)	6 injection cycles over a 2-day period	95.53%	MICP reduced porosity and permeability while increasing capillary pressure; limited impact of dissolution due to preferential sealing of flow paths.

3.1. Continuum and multiphysics modeling

At the macroscale, the effectiveness of MICP is governed by complex bio-chemo-hydro-mechanical (BCHM) couplings. Kashizadeh et al. [136] emphasizes that a robust numerical model must account for the reactive transport of nutrients and bacteria alongside the kinetics of urea hydrolysis. To describe the mechanical consequence of these processes, Gai and Sánchez [137] developed an elastoplastic constitutive model that incorporates a critical state framework and sub-loading surface concepts. This model is particularly effective at capturing the bonding enhancement provided by calcite and the subsequent degradation or damage softening of these bonds during shearing. Furthermore, recent efforts have focused on the spatial heterogeneity inherent in large-scale treatments. As noted by Evans et al. [138] and Kashizadeh et al. [136], models that assume homogenized cementation often fail to predict localized failure zones; therefore, integrating spatial-temporal variations in cement distribution is essential for reliable stability analysis.

3.2. Micro-mechanical analysis

DEM has become the primary tool for investigating the micro-origins of the macroscopic behavior of biocemented soils. Early models represented cementation as parallel bonds [139]; however, recent research has transitioned toward more realistic representations of mineral morphology. Wu et al. [140] introduced a 3D DEM scheme using fine particles as cementing agents to reproduce diverse precipitation patterns, effective bridging, surface coating, and pore filling, revealing that the finite-strain mechanical response is highly sensitive to the topological relation between calcite and sand grains.

The precipitation pattern's impact on stiffness and strength has been further clarified through DEM probing of small-strain properties. Zhang et al. [141] identified two primary mechanisms of reinforcement: the increase in contact number (coordination number) and the enhancement of individual contact stiffness. Their findings suggest that cementation localized at grain contacts maximizes the initial shear modulus (G_0), while minerals distributed in the pore space contribute minimally to mechanical stability. This is supported by Sun et al. [142], who utilized DEM to model shear wave propagation, demonstrating that V_s measurements are a direct proxy for the evolution of effective contact bonds rather than total carbonate mass.

To improve predictive accuracy, researchers have begun investigating the micromechanics of dual-particle interactions. Liu et al. [143,144] conducted DEM-based pull-out and tensile tests, uncovering a transition in failure modes from internal cohesive failure of the calcite crystal to adhesive debonding at the grain-calcite interface, depending on the cementation radius and interfacial strength. These particle-scale insights are now being integrated into hierarchical bottom-up models. Zhao et al. [145] proposed a three-level hierarchical DEM framework that upscales microscopic crystal distributions into generalized Equivalent Cementation Bonds (ECB), enabling large-scale simulations that remain grounded in pore-scale physics. Finally, the role of inherent anisotropy and particle shape (e.g., elliptical or polygonal grains) has been highlighted as a critical factor in the shear strength and dilatancy of biocemented assemblies [146,147].

4. Injection strategies

The introduction and retention of ureolytic bacteria or urease enzymes within the soil matrix or rock joints is a key component of MICP in order to ensure successful ground improvement. By injecting a cementation solution into the retained bacteria, CaCO_3 precipitation can be induced. Thus, ensuring the proper distribution and retention of these bacteria is crucial for uniform CaCO_3 formation. This is where injection strategies come into play. Various injection strategies are employed to deliver the bacteria and cementation solution to the soil or rock discontinuities, each with its own advantages and limitations for effectively retaining bacteria and achieving the desired soil and rock improvement. Different methods are available to introduce bacteria into soil, which are presented as follows.

4.1. Direct injection

Direct injection is the most commonly used MICP treatment for laboratory soil samples, where bacterial and reagent solutions are mixed together and pumped through the soil from one end to the other at a controlled flow or pressure, as shown in Fig. 11(a). This MICP treatment method relies on injection conditions, such as flow, pressure, and hydraulic gradient, that can be easily controlled during testing. This method can be applicable in soils with various saturation levels due to its adjustable flow, but it often leads to uneven distribution of CaCO_3 and bacteria, particularly in sands and high-permeability soils, due to rapid clogging and localized cementation, resulting in uneven reinforcement of bio-cemented soil strength in tested columns [30,148–150]. To overcome the clogging issue of one-phase injection, Whiffin et al. [39] introduced a two-phase injection strategy to treat a 5 m long sandy soil column in which both the bacteria culture and the cementation solution were injected at low pressures without clogging the material. The treated sand column showed CaCO_3 precipitation along its entire 5 m length, although the distribution of CaCO_3 was not uniform.

To achieve uniform bacterial activity, Harkes et al. [30] introduced a two-phase injection method using 50 mM calcium chloride (CaCl_2) as a fixation solution. The procedure began with injection of the bacterial suspension, followed by reagent injection, and a high-salinity fixation solution in between, which promoted bacterial adsorption by reducing repulsive electrostatic forces between soil particles and bacterial cells. This was effective in enhancing bacterial retention within the soil sample. A retention period was also incorporated to further improve the process, allowing repeated reagent injections without reaction time delays, known as staged injection. This method, now widely used in MICP soil strengthening, enables continuous urease activity by periodically adding bacterial solutions, resulting in higher calcite content and more uniform distribution [15,151–157].

To examine the effect of different injection strategies (i.e., parallel and staged injections) on the distribution of filled pore space, Tobler et al. [158] carried out unidirectional flow-through experiments in sand columns. Under parallel injection, where the ureolytic bacterium *Sporosarcina pasteurii* and the cementation solution were injected simultaneously, calcite precipitation was heterogeneous, with most CaCO_3 forming near the inlet. In contrast, staged injection of bacteria followed by cementation solution produced a gradient fill of calcite along the flow path, with the highest percentage farther along the column compared to continuous parallel injection. Using staged injection, porosity was reduced by 54%, compared with 34% for parallel injection.

Apart from experimental studies, Wang et al. [159] investigated the optimization of injection strategies by simulating continuous and staged injection methods. They applied a Darcy-scale mathematical model to simulate MICP processes under different scenarios. Results showed an almost 24% increase in precipitated calcite mass for staged injection compared with continuous injection, highlighting the advantage of staged injection when additional reaction time is provided after fluid delivery.

4.2. Premixing method

The premixing method involves mechanically mixing the bacteria and reagents with soil in a controlled environment before application until the desired homogeneity is achieved. The addition of the cementation solution to the bacteria prior to injection causes an immediate reaction that results in the precipitation of CaCO_3 and the flocculation of bacterial cells. This method is suitable for treating a wide range of soil types, including clean sands and certain types of clays [151]. However, it is generally considered

Fig. 11. Schematic view of different injection strategies used in MICP technique: (a) direct injection mode [39] and (b) percolation method [160].

most effective for treating coarse materials requiring higher reaction rates and larger amounts of precipitate, which also provides several advantages [161]. Requiring less injection time simplifies the overall process and reduces costs in practical applications. Additionally, the premixing method eliminates the need for injection pumps and specialized equipment, further streamlining the procedure and lowering labor demands.

Wu et al. [162] conducted experimental tests to assess the premixed injection method with and without pH adjustment for stabilizing coarse aggregates ranging from 0.75 to 10 mm. One of the shortcomings of this method is that the premixed bacterial suspension and cementation solution tend to form bacterial flocs before injection; however, this issue can be mitigated by adjusting the pH of the solution. The results demonstrated that both premixed injection methods, with or without bacterial flocs, were effective in increasing the strength of coarse aggregates with grain sizes larger than 2 mm. On the other hand, for fine aggregates with grain sizes within 0.75–2 mm, a significant difference in strength was observed between samples treated with or without bacterial flocs. This indicates that the premixing injection method is not suitable for fine aggregates.

To study the effectiveness of the multiple-phase injection method and the premixing method in improving the mechanical properties of Yellow River silt, Wang et al. [163] performed MICP solidification tests under different cementation solution concentrations and treatment durations. The results showed that the premixing method was 5% more efficient than multiple-phase injection in terms of chemical conversion. Moreover, in the premixing method, calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) distribution and unconfined compressive strength (UCS) increased more rapidly as the cementation solution concentration and treatment time were increased. Despite solving the homogeneity issue, the premixing method remains the least favorable MICP approach due to the disturbance it causes to the local soil structure and the potential formation of pseudo-stresses, which complicates the stress history [148]. Despite solving the homogeneity issue, the premixing method remains the least favorable MICP approach due to the mechanical disturbance of the soil structure and the development of pseudo-stresses. Pseudo-stresses refer to the unmeasured mechanical stresses applied to the soil during the vigorous mixing of the soil matrix with the bacterial and cementing solutions, which may disturb the original soil fabric and modify the local stress history prior to mechanical testing, contributing to inaccurate strength measurements.

4.3. Percolation method

The percolation method was first developed by Cheng and Cord-Ruwisch [164]. It involves spraying bacterial and reagent solutions onto the soil surface, allowing infiltration through gravity and capillary forces for shallow-depth treatment. This method is simpler than pressurized injection, as it requires no heavy machinery and can be applied across various saturation levels, although it may have limitations in fine-grained soils such as silt or clay due to low infiltration rates and permeability [15,148]. The percolation method has been applied in various MICP-related studies [42,165–168].

For instance, Mahawish et al. [169] adopted a two-phase percolation approach to investigate the feasibility of a soil-lift biogrouting treatment strategy to improve the mechanical characteristics of coarse sand, specifically for granular column applications. According to their findings, increasing the number of soil lifts adversely affected the mechanical properties of the biocemented sand. In contrast, a single-lift treatment produced significant improvements, yielding strength and stiffness increments of up to 8.9 MPa and

2.3 GPa, respectively. In another study, Kou et al. [170] examined surface percolation for reinforcing sandy slopes under unsaturated conditions using laboratory-scale models of coastal slopes treated with MICP to evaluate erosion resistance. Biocement distribution within the slope was measured to understand the mechanism. Results showed no noticeable erosion on the slope surface after four MICP treatment cycles. Saturation levels were lowest at the slope crest and increased toward the slope toe, contributing to doubled erosion resistance from top to bottom due to water movement. Fig. 11(b) illustrates the schematic of the sand column setup treated via MICP percolation [160].

A major limitation in surface percolation and traditional spraying methods is the lack of depth control, which is often simplified in laboratory studies. However, recent large-scale calcareous sand tests showed that the initial water level can strongly alter the complex spatial competition between infiltration and precipitation mechanisms. Using *Sporosarcina pasteurii* in a 30 cm diameter, 100 cm high column, Li et al. [171] compared dry, partially saturated, and fully saturated initial states. It was revealed that the initial water level is a key control factor of reinforcement depth, in such a way that a fully saturated state inhibits deep precipitation, forming only a thin surface crust. In contrast, an initial water level of 0.5 m uses capillary action to help microorganisms migrate to the deeper particle contact points (cementation with a depth of 60 cm), resulting in more particle bridging rather than particle wrapping. Furthermore, the results indicated that biogenic CaCO_3 also modified the soil–water characteristic response of calcareous sand. As cementation increased, the SWRC shifted upward and the matrix suction at the same volumetric water content increased, indicating that MICP improved the water-retention capacity of the sand through pore blocking and progressive reduction of intergranular pore space [171].

Considering the advantages and drawbacks of these injection strategies, each method can be selectively applied based on soil type, treatment scale, and project-specific objectives. In a comprehensive study, Shahrokhi-Shahraki et al. [149] tested and compared several injection strategies, including mixing, two-phase injection, staged injection, and single-phase injection for MICP treatment of sand. They found that staged injection with retention periods and pressure-head application during bacterial cell injection was the most effective. More recently, Zeitouny et al. [9] introduced a new MICP treatment approach combining premixing, percolation, and submerging methods to investigate strength and the homogeneity of calcium carbonate distribution in artificial sandstone production. This hybrid method was developed to exploit the strengths of each strategy. Comparisons were made between Portland-cement and MICP-cemented sand treated via percolation and combined methods. Portland-cement specimens exhibited UCS values ranging from 0.6 MPa to 17.2 MPa, corresponding to cementation levels between 5% and 30%. For MICP-cemented sand, the percolation method yielded UCS values of 0.5–0.9 MPa, while the combined method achieved strengths up to 3.7 MPa. Additionally, specimens treated with the combined method exhibited a more uniform distribution of CaCO_3 throughout the soil matrix.

Overall, selecting the injection mode is closely linked to the feasible treatment scale of the MICP technique, which determines the reachable volume and depth of the treated zone. Direct injection is the most commonly used approach for laboratory soil samples because hydraulic conditions can be controlled relatively well, making it suitable for element-scale and many meso-scale studies, although clogging and non-uniform CaCO_3 distribution may become more pronounced as treatment volume increases. When it comes to the premixing method, it may improve homogeneity at the specimen scale, but its application is generally restricted to element-scale laboratory tests or small precast units, since the high energy required for soil disturbance is not practical for large in-situ volumes. In contrast, the percolation method is effective for broad surface and shallow treatment applications at the meso or field-scale, because of its simple operation and lower equipment demand. Therefore, injection mode selection directly influences treatment depth, spatial uniformity, and scale-up feasibility, which in turn governs the feasible treatment scale that is discussed in detail in the next section.

5. Treatment scale

The characteristics of bio-cemented soil have been studied at numerous scales using various testing methods. As research in this field continues to expand, it becomes necessary to categorize the extensive findings into distinct scales to facilitate a comprehensive understanding of the methodology's applicability and effectiveness, and to enable observation of how micro-scale responses are linked to large-scale behavior. In this context, we aim to organize and present the diverse studies in the MICP domain through a systematic classification consisting of three distinct scales: *element tests*, *mesoscale tests*, and *large-scale tests*.

5.1. Element tests

At the small scale, element tests have been conducted to examine the fundamental processes and interactions involved in the MICP technique. These studies serve as the building blocks for understanding the behavior of soils and rocks under various conditions before moving to larger-scale investigations. Triaxial tests, a key experimental method, simulate in-situ stress conditions and measure stiffness, shear strength, and dilatancy. In general, triaxial testing indicates that peak strength, stress ratio (i.e., deviator stress to mean effective stress), and initial stiffness increase after biological treatment, while the stress–strain response transitions from strain hardening to strain softening, and residual strength increases only marginally [15]. These trends result from microstructural changes that occur during loading. The formation of CaCO_3 crystals leads to a cemented structure similar to naturally or artificially cemented soils [172,173]. This structure strengthens the soil matrix, making it stiffer and less prone to deformation during initial loading, while also making the overall response more brittle due to the fragile nature of CaCO_3 bonds.

To investigate the effects of MICP treatment on the stress–strain–strength behavior of sand, Wu et al. [174] performed isotropically consolidated drained triaxial tests. Their findings revealed pronounced dilatancy in bio-cemented sand, whereas untreated sand of the same density exhibited contractive behavior. The treatment effects were reflected in a continuous increase in

Fig. 12. Relationship between cyclic improvement factor (I_f) of MICP-treated sands with calcium carbonate contents [177–179,182]. Source: Modified from [181].

cohesion (from 0 to 0.5 MPa) and a limited increase in the internal friction angle (from 32° to 45°), with no further improvement beyond a CaCO_3 content of 14%. Similar observations were reported by Liu et al. [175], who identified an exponential increase in c' , while ϕ' remained essentially unchanged. Soil stiffness is another critical parameter for evaluating the behavior of MICP-enhanced soil, as it directly relates to the bonding strength among particles. The bender element test is commonly used to measure shear wave velocity and thus determine small-strain stiffness. MICP treatment has been demonstrated to significantly increase shear stiffness and improve the overall stability of treated soils compared with untreated soils [14,176].

Element tests also play an important role in assessing liquefaction resistance in MICP-treated specimens. Using stress-controlled undrained cyclic triaxial tests, Xiao et al. [177] demonstrated that MICP can shift the liquefaction failure mechanism from flow failure to cyclic mobility, significantly altering the pore pressure generation characteristics of loose specimens. The direct simple shear (DSS) test has also been widely used to simulate cyclic shear loading during earthquakes. Based on the study by Riveros and Sadrekarimi [178], MICP treatment enhances the liquefaction resistance criterion by increasing the number of cycles required to reach liquefaction (N_L) from 14 to 94, an approximately 6.7-fold improvement. The MICP-treated samples also exhibited 67% greater cyclic resistance at 15 cycles compared to untreated sand, indicating a substantial enhancement that exceeds improvements typically achieved through densification alone. Similar increases in liquefaction resistance due to MICP treatment have been reported in other DSS studies [179,180].

Recently, the *cyclic improvement factor* (I_f), defined as the ratio of the cyclic stress ratio required to trigger liquefaction in a treated sample to that of an untreated one, has been introduced as a quantitative measure of MICP effectiveness [181]. This measure enables systematic comparison across different studies. Fig. 12 summarizes reported I_f values from several works [177–179,182]. In general, higher treatment levels correspond to increased cyclic improvement, although the rate of improvement varies across experiments. Variability arises due to differences in geomaterials, treatment techniques, relative densities, and testing apparatus. Nevertheless, broader adoption of the I_f metric would facilitate more consistent comparisons and enhance interpretation of liquefaction mitigation through MICP. Table 6 summarizes the key findings from element tests conducted to evaluate the influence of MICP treatment on various soil properties.

5.2. Meso-scale tests

Beyond element tests, mesoscale tests have been used to bridge the gap between laboratory experiments and real-world applications. This category explores MICP under conditions that mimic field scenarios at a more substantial scale, offering insights into practical implications while remaining within laboratory constraints. Mesoscale testing provides a middle ground between controlled element testing and large-scale implementation, enabling improved understanding of how localized micro-scale processes influence broader soil behavior.

An upscaling experiment was carried out by Martinez [186] using a target treatment area of $0.5 \text{ m} \times 0.5 \text{ m} \times 0.15 \text{ m}$. Inhomogeneous CaCO_3 distribution across the soil matrix was frequently observed at the meso-scale, whereas at the micro-scale, CaCO_3 distribution at the interparticle level contributed to strength enhancement. To assess the potential of biogrouting for field applications, Van Paassen et al. [187] developed a multibox container setup ($0.9 \text{ m} \times 1.1 \text{ m} \times 1 \text{ m}^3$) with drainage filters installed on the sides to mimic a spherical injection source. Two types of sand were treated with 3500 L and 4000 L of reagent solutions, respectively. CaCO_3 precipitation varied between 100 and 250 kg/m^3 in the sandbox, producing manual cone penetration resistances above 5 MPa and UCS values over 9 MPa near the surface.

Phillips et al. [188] designed and built a mesoscale high-pressure vessel capable of accommodating rock cores up to 74 cm in diameter and 50 cm in height to investigate MICP for reducing the permeability of a sandstone hydraulic fracture under simulated

Table 6

Summary of different studies using element tests evaluating the effects of MICP treatment on various soil properties (CD: Consolidated drained, CU: Consolidated undrained, DSS: Direct simple shear).

Reference	Element test type	Material	Characteristics assessed	Impact of MICP treatment
Li [183]	Triaxial (CD)	Ottawa sand	Shear strength	Shear strength increase due to enhanced bonding
Nafisi et al. [184]	Triaxial (CD)	Ottawa and Nevada sand	Peak shear strength, post-peak behavior	Up to 17× shear strength increase; notable strain-softening post-peak
Wu et al. [174]	Triaxial (CD)	Sand	Cohesion, internal friction angle	High dilatancy in bio-treated sand; cohesion increased from 0 to 0.5 MPa; limited increase in friction angle for 14% CaCO ₃
DeJong et al. [14]	Triaxial (CU), Bender Element	Loose-collapsible sand	Shear wave velocity, shear stiffness	Higher initial shear stiffness and increased ultimate shear capacity
Montoya and DeJong [176]	Triaxial (CD, CU), Bender Element	Sand	Shear strength and stiffness	Significant strength and stiffness improvement with increased cementation
Xiao et al. [182]	Cyclic Triaxial (CU)	Yongxing calcareous sand	Liquefaction resistance	Improved liquefaction resistance and surface roughness due to interparticle void filling
Burbank et al. [185]	Cyclic Triaxial	Sand	Cyclic resistance	2–4× increase in cyclic resistance with CaCO ₃ contents of 2.2–7.4%
Riveros and Sadrekarimi [178]	Direct Simple Shear (DSS)	Fraser River sand	Liquefaction resistance	Liquefaction resistance increased by 6.7%; 67% improvement in cyclic resistance at 15 cycles

in situ pressures (45 bar). Initial experiments showed that 20 days were required to achieve the targeted permeability reduction, which is too long for practical field deployment. To decrease sealing time, daily pulsing of calcium and microbial growth solutions was introduced, improving the biomineralization efficiency. Overall, the study demonstrated that MICP can reduce permeability in mineralized fractures by more than two orders of magnitude under subsurface conditions. More recently, Zamani et al. [189] used centrifuge modeling to evaluate MICP-treated loose sand for improving liquefaction resistance and reducing total and differential settlement of shallow foundations. The results showed that MICP treatment increased liquefaction resistance and reduced total settlement and maximum angular distortion of foundation system by up to 57% and 75%, respectively, depending on soil layering and MICP treatment depth.

5.3. Logistical and technical challenges in upscaling

The transition from controlled laboratory element tests (e.g., triaxial or unconfined compression columns) to large-scale and field applications introduces a multitude of logistical and engineering challenges [37,148]. While microscopic and element-scale studies isolate specific variables to understand fundamental mechanisms, field-scale implementation requires managing complex, coupled processes over large volumes. Addressing these logistical challenges is a prerequisite for transitioning MICP from a laboratory phenomenon to a viable geotechnical construction technique [13,190].

Firstly, the biological cultivation and transportation of microorganisms present a primary logistical hurdle. At the element scale, bacterial strains are cultured in small, highly controlled, and sterile environments. Upscaling requires the use of industrial-scale bioreactors to produce hundreds or thousands of liters of active bacterial culture [13]. Maintaining the viability and optimum urease activity of these cultures during transportation, storage, and injection under fluctuating in-situ environmental conditions requires robust supply chain management. To circumvent the high costs and logistical complexities of sterile transport, field studies have increasingly explored the biostimulation of indigenous ureolytic bacteria or the use of non-sterile, technical-grade cultivation [165,191].

Secondly, achieving a homogeneous distribution of calcium carbonate across large soil domains remains technically difficult. In natural deposits, soil heterogeneity leads to preferential fluid flow paths. Furthermore, rapid precipitation near the injection points often causes localized pore clogging, which significantly reduces hydraulic conductivity and prevents the cementation solution from reaching the intended treatment radius [30,158]. Consequently, field logistics demand sophisticated injection strategies, such as staged injections, pulsed pumping, or the continuous circulation of reagents between injection and extraction wells, to optimize flow rates and ensure uniform delivery [13,158].

Thirdly, the environmental management of chemical by-products scales proportionally with the treatment volume. The ureolysis-driven MICP process inherently generates equimolar amounts of ammonium alongside carbonate. While easily managed or flushed in small laboratory elements, the accumulation of high concentrations of ammonium in large-scale applications poses a severe contamination risk to local groundwater and terrestrial ecosystems [192]. Field implementations must therefore logistically incorporate effluent extraction systems, post-treatment flushing regimens, or coupled biological processes to mitigate nitrogenous by-products before they migrate off-site [193].

Table 7
Overview of large-scale MICP investigations reported by different researchers.

Reference	Focus of study	Application/Scale area (boundary)	Key outcomes/Observations
van Paassen et al. [13]	Strength and stiffness in fine sand	MICP injection in fine sand/100 m ³ (Controlled)	Shear wave velocity (V_s) ranged from 188–395 m/s; UCS values between 0.7–12 MPa; good correlation between in situ and empirical stiffness measurements.
Harran et al. [197]	Efficiency of ex-situ hydrolysis for bio-cementation	Bio-cementation/40 m ² (Controlled)	Achieved similar CaCO ₃ precipitation levels and mechanical gains compared with in-situ methods.
Gomez et al. [190]	Dust erosion mitigation on loose sand	Surface spraying at mine site/35 m ² (Open-field)	Created a crust layer 0.6–2 cm thick; increased penetration resistance up to 40 cm depth.
Ghasemi and Montoya [198]	Surface erosion control	Surface spraying on coastal sandy slope/3.3 m ² (Open-field)	Precipitation reached 18–20 cm depth; improved penetration resistance and reduced erosion.
Van Paassen [199]	Stabilizing gravel for borehole stability	Horizontal directional drilling in gravel (Open-field)	Stabilized gravel layers effectively; successful pipeline installation without soil collapse.
Terzis et al. [200]	Landslide risk mitigation	Slip zone stabilization in Switzerland/51 m ² (Open-field)	Slowed slope movement through calcite binder formation; effective when combined with drainage trenches.

Finally, the economic logistics of material procurement shift drastically. The reliance on laboratory-grade chemical reagents (e.g., calcium chloride, urea) and high-cost nutrient broths is financially prohibitive at the field scale [192]. Upscaling necessitates establishing local supply chains for technical-grade chemicals, industrial by-products, or agricultural waste derivatives to serve as economical calcium and nutrient sources, ensuring the treatment remains cost-competitive with traditional chemical stabilizers [165, 194].

5.4. Large-scale tests

Large-scale tests address real-world challenges and evaluate the practical effectiveness of MICP under in situ conditions. These tests provide valuable data for validating laboratory findings and developing predictive models, which are essential for implementing the technique on engineering project scales. Generally, large-scale investigations fall into two main categories: (a) controlled custom-built systems, in which geomaterials, treatments, and boundary conditions are carefully managed, and (b) open-limit conditions such as pilot projects or field trials, where natural soil conditions and boundary constraints are less controllable.

As one of the first large-scale controlled experiments, van Paassen et al. [13] injected *Sporosarcina pasteurii* into 100 m³ of fine sand. Shear-wave velocity (V_s) values ranged from 188 to 395 m/s depending on location. With CaCO₃ contents of 12%–27%, UCS values ranged from 0.7 to 12 MPa, and Young's modulus ranged from 0.1 to 13 GPa. Notably, time-lapse seismic measurements aligned well with empirical UCS-based stiffness correlations. Similar large-scale trials have demonstrated increases in both UCS and V_s , confirming enhanced strength and stiffness from MICP treatment [191,195,196].

Harran et al. [197] introduced a state-of-the-art installation enabling bio-cementation over a volume of 40 m² to depths of 2 m at the Laboratory of Soil Mechanics, EPFL. The study deployed an ex-situ hydrolysis strategy, where urea hydrolysis occurs in bioreactors rather than within the soil mass. This approach achieved precipitation efficiencies and mechanical improvements comparable to traditional in situ bio-cementation techniques. CaCO₃ contents between 4% and 10% yielded UCS values up to 2.1 MPa and elastic moduli up to 480 MPa. When bio-cementation is applied in natural environments under open-limit conditions, treatment protocols differ significantly. To evaluate surficial MICP treatment for dust erosion mitigation at a mine site in Canada, Gomez et al. [190] sprayed 22.7 m³ of treatment solutions over a 35 m² area. Dynamic cone penetration testing and CaCO₃ measurements assessed improvements to 40 cm depth. Observed crust thickness was 0.6–2 cm, and dual-mass cone penetrometer blow counts increased to 1–3 blows/cm.

In another field study, 5.7 m³ of MICP solutions were sprayed over an 8 m² coastal sandy slope in the United States to mitigate surface erosion [198]. CaCO₃ precipitation penetrated 18–20 cm below the surface, and penetration indices improved from 9 cm/blow to 3.5 cm/blow. For borehole instability in gravel, Van Paassen [199] conducted laboratory trials on a 3 m³ gravel-filled container before full-scale field implementation. At field scale, 1000 m³ of soil was treated with 200 m³ of bacterial suspension and 300–600 m³ of cementation solution at depths of 3–20 m. The treated gravel layer remained stable during horizontal directional drilling, enabling successful pipeline installation.

In Switzerland, a novel MICP technique based on ex-situ hydrolysis was implemented to mitigate landslide risk by inducing subsurface calcite precipitation within a slip zone [200]. Approximately 4 m³ of solution was injected, accompanied by drainage trench installations. Laboratory testing, in situ monitoring, microstructural investigations, and post-stabilization aerial observations confirmed reduced slope movement in treated areas relative to untreated surroundings. Table 7 summarizes reported large-scale MICP applications in the literature.

In addition to field trials, recent controlled large-scale flume tests have been performed to overcome the boundary effects and sensor inaccuracies common in small laboratory columns, bridging the methodological gap between small laboratory erosion

Table 8

Cross-scale comparative synthesis of MICP processes from micro- to large-scale applications [8,9,12,13,15,30,61,157,177,181,203,204].

Scale	Primary mechanisms	Key controlling parameters	Outcomes	Uncertainties
Micro-scale	Urea hydrolysis kinetics; enzyme activity; crystal nucleation.	pH; temperature; bacterial activity; urea concentration	Crystal formation; bonding initiation; pore-throat clogging; inter-particle bond strength	Cell viability under high Ca^{2+} ; localized pH fluctuations; premature cell encapsulation.
Element-scale	Urea hydrolysis rates; Particle bonding; pore filling	Injection mode, solution concentration, curing time	Strength increase; permeability reduction	Sample disturbance; non-uniform distribution; boundary effects
Meso-scale	Transport-reaction coupling, spatial heterogeneity	Flow regime, saturation, injection strategy	Spatial distribution of calcite; clogging at injection points; gradients in CaCO_3 content; breakthrough curves	Preferential flow paths (channeling); nutrient depletion along the flow path; scale-dependent dispersivity
Large-scale	Large-scale pumping mechanics; load transfer; environmental boundary conditions.	Soil variability; environmental conditions; delivery method	Bearing capacity and durability increment; ground improvement; large-scale crack healing; total CO_2 sequestration volume	Upscaling uncertainty; cost; clogging; groundwater flow dilution; long-term performance; byproduct management (NH_3)

studies and field-relevant coastal conditions [201]. Accordingly, MICP-treated sandy slopes were examined in a 69 m long, 1.2 m wide, and 1.6 m high flume, using a 4 m long and 0.6 m high slope of Fujian sand with wave gauges and pore-pressure sensors installed around the surf zone. By combining wave gauges, pore-pressure sensors, penetration testing, and post-test calcium carbonate measurements in a large flume, it was shown that MICP treatment can stabilize surf-zone topography and maintain a more regular wave-breaking pattern, whereas untreated slopes undergo pronounced reshaping under repeated wave action, increasing erosive energy. Additionally, while the accumulation of crystals reduces permeability, it significantly increases the excess pore water pressure gradient in the shallow layer, which must be accounted for in the hydraulic design of bio-cemented coastal slopes. To further evaluate the stability of such reinforced environments under wave action, Li et al. [202] developed a comprehensive bio-chemo-hydro-wave (B-C-H-W) coupled mathematical model. Their simulations revealed the dynamic response of wave-induced pore pressures within the MICP-treated seabed, demonstrating that optimized spatial arrangements, such as flower and spot grouting, can significantly enhance the overall liquefaction resistance of the sandy seabed.

While the preceding sections provide individual studies at various scales, Table 8 presents a cross-scale synthesis of MICP applications from micro to large scale. The table compares the primary mechanisms, key controlling parameters, outcomes, and major uncertainties associated with each scale. In this way, the table provides a concise overview of how the governing processes and engineering implications of MICP change across scales.

6. Durability and long-term performance of MICP-treated geomaterials

The successful application and widespread adoption of MICP technology, particularly in geotechnical and infrastructural contexts, fundamentally rely on establishing the durability and long-term performance of the treated geomaterials [205]. While initial studies confirmed the high efficiency of MICP in augmenting strength and stiffness, extensive comparative research has now focused on quantifying performance degradation under environmental stressors, addressing the critical necessity for robust, quantitative evaluations prior to widespread field deployment [206].

6.1. Short-term and long-term durability metrics

Durability assessment involves monitoring the mechanical and hydraulic stability of MICP-treated materials before and after exposure to adverse environmental or mechanical conditions. Short-term performance is typically evaluated through fundamental mechanical indicators. In granular soils, the enhancement of UCS serves as a primary metric for early-age improvement. Optimized MICP treatment protocols, such as those applied to silty sand (0.75 mol/L cementation solution, 90% relative compaction, 21 treatment cycles), have been shown to increase UCS from an untreated baseline of approximately 200–250 kPa to peak strengths approaching 1030 kPa [207]. Other immediate performance enhancements include increases in shear wave velocity (V_s), which reflect the development and continuity of calcite cementation bonds [179], as well as substantial reductions in hydraulic conductivity due to progressive pore filling and interparticle bonding [149].

Long-term durability, conversely, focuses on the retention of these initial improvements when MICP-treated geomaterials are subjected to sustained or cyclic environmental stressors. Key evaluation metrics include the UCS loss rate and the Strength Deterioration Ratio (SDR) [208,209]. The SDR, defined as $1 - \text{UCS}(f)/\text{UCS}(i)$, quantifies the proportion of strength lost after exposure to adverse conditions. Mass loss measurements are also commonly employed to track the physical disintegration of specimens and the detachment or dissolution of CaCO_3 bonds [208,210]. Dynamic stiffness parameters provide additional insight into long-term mechanical degradation. For example, the secant modulus (E_{50}) has been shown to experience substantial reductions—often exceeding 50% after 12 freeze–thaw cycles in some MICP-treated sands—whereas the constrained modulus (D) typically exhibits more moderate deterioration, on the order of approximately 10.9% over the same number of cycles [207]. Furthermore, in cementitious systems, the longevity, viability, and reactivation potential of microbial agents constitute critical long-term durability

indicators, as these factors govern the capacity for continued mineralization and autonomous healing over extended service periods [211].

To improve cross-comparison between durability studies, a minimum standardized testing framework is suggested for MICP-treated geomaterials, based on the literature [208,209]:

1. All specimens should be prepared to a target dry density and initial moisture content, reporting at least the geomaterial type, initial mass, initial void ratio, and specimen dimensions.
2. For element tests, cylindrical specimens with a height-to-diameter ratio of 2:1 are recommended.
3. Before environmental exposure, the initial value of UCS(i).
4. Standardized WD cycling (adapted ASTM D559/D559M-15): Specimens should completely be immersed in the distilled water in room temperature (25 ± 1 °C) for 6 h throughout the wetting procedure, followed by a minimum of 42 h of oven drying at 60 ± 1 °C. 12, 20, and 50 cycles of WD are recommended.
5. Standardized FT cycling (adapted ASTM D560): Specimens should be frozen at -18 °C for 24 h, followed by 24 h thawing at room temperature (23 °C). 20 cycles of FT are recommended.
6. Calculate $SDR = 1 - UCS(f)/UCS(i)$, where UCS(i) is the baseline strength of non-cycled control specimens and UCS(f) is the average strength after n cycles of environmental stress.
7. Calculate Mass Loss Rate ($MLR = 1 - m(f)/m(i)$), where $m(i)$ is the mass of sample before environmental conditions and $m(f)$ is mass of sample after n cycles of environmental stress.

6.2. Durability of MICP-treated soils under environmental cycling

6.2.1. Element tests

MICP-treated geomaterials frequently experience durability challenges when exposed to natural environmental cycles. Among the most influential of these are wetting–drying (WD) and freeze–thaw (FT) cycles, each inducing distinct degradation mechanisms. Comparative studies consistently demonstrate that WD cycling is significantly more destructive than FT cycling, particularly for specimens with low to moderate cementation levels [208,212,213].

The higher destructiveness of WD cycling compared to FT cycling is rooted in distinct pore-scale mechanisms. In WD cycles, the primary degradation is driven by the immediate destabilization of the organic–mineral interface. When water penetrates the pore system during the wetting phase, powdery bonds, loosely attached, and poorly crystallized $CaCO_3$ clusters are forced into suspension and subsequently eroded, reducing the integrity of the cemented skeleton [205,208]. In addition, during the drying phase, the evaporation of pore fluid leads to the development of matric suction, which generates significantly high tensile and shear stresses on the rigid $CaCO_3$ mineral bridges, leading to progressive fatigue and micro-cracking of the cementation bonds [206,214,215]. In contrast, while the degradation mechanism during freeze-thaw cycles is predominantly physical and driven by the volumetric expansion (approximately 9%) of pore water upon transition to ice [216], the presence of Extracellular Polymeric Substances (EPS) often acts as a ductile buffer. This organic matrix can accommodate a portion of the ice-induced expansion, whereas the rigid shrinkage-swelling induced by WD leads to a more rapid loss of structural integrity [213].

Furthermore, the long-term durability is heavily influenced by crystal polymorphism. While calcite remains the most thermodynamically stable phase, providing high mechanical resistance, the presence of metastable vaterite can compromise durability. The eventual transformation of vaterite into calcite via dissolution-reprecipitation can initiate internal micro-stresses and volume changes, potentially weakening the biomineralized framework [217]. The stability of the organic-mineral interface also plays a critical role; EPS serves as a nucleation template and protective sheath, where electrostatic interactions between microbial functional groups and Ca^{2+} ions enhance the adhesion between the mineral precipitates and the soil grains [218]. The degradation of these organic bridges under extreme conditions can accelerate the detachment of crystals, leading to the increased mass loss observed in durability testing.

An extensive body of work (e.g., [208,212,213]) has shown that WD cycling poses the greatest threat to the integrity of MICP-treated soils, often resulting in rapid loss of stiffness, cementation, and cohesion. This vulnerability arises from dissolution, detachment, and suspension of loosely bonded, poorly crystallized $CaCO_3$ precipitates that accumulate on particle surfaces. One of the most striking observations was provided by Liu et al. [208], who documented an approximately 80% drop in UCS after only a single WD cycle in MICP-treated sand. This phenomenon, termed Short-Term Deterioration (STD), reflects the immediate destabilization of fragile $CaCO_3$ clusters. Similar behaviors are observed in expansive soils. During the first 5–9 WD cycles, reductions in UCS and cohesion progress rapidly, after which the deterioration rate stabilizes as remaining bonds are more robust and better integrated within the soil skeleton [146].

Durability improvements can be achieved through reinforcement strategies. Jute fibers [209] and basalt fibers [219] substantially mitigate WD-induced degradation. For example, Rawat and Satyam [219] found that an optimal basalt fiber content of 0.40% limited mass loss to only 3.53% after 15 WD cycles in coastal sand. Fiber reinforcement enhances durability by providing mechanical anchorage, reducing crack propagation, and distributing stresses around degrading $CaCO_3$ bonds. Solution concentration also plays a critical role. Lower cementation concentrations (e.g., 0.25 M Ca^{2+}) are insufficient to resist rainfall-induced surface erosion, whereas higher concentrations produce thicker and more coherent $CaCO_3$ crusts, improving resistance to WD cycling [220].

Direct comparisons by Ren et al. [213] highlight the significantly harsher impact of WD cycling relative to FT cycling for MICP-treated poorly graded sand (Fig. 13). After 9 cycles, WD-treated specimens retained only 34.1% of their initial UCS, roughly half of the retention observed for FT-treated specimens (64.6%). Likewise, mass loss in WD samples was 1.67 times higher. These

Fig. 13. Deterioration process of MICP-treated poorly graded sand during FT and WD cycles in terms of (a) UCS and (b) mass retention [213].

observations confirm that WD cycles primarily remove cementing products by dissolution and particle detachment, while FT cycles cause microcracking due to pore water expansion with comparatively lower mass loss.

Although FT cycles also induce deterioration, MICP-treated soils generally exhibit moderate to strong resilience, particularly when cementation is dense and uniformly distributed. Gowthaman et al. [205] demonstrated that FT durability is strongly controlled by CaCO_3 content. Highly cemented specimens (20%–23% CaCO_3) exhibited exceptional resistance to FT-induced damage, showing only 2% mass loss after 25 FT cycles. In contrast, weakly cemented specimens (11%–13% CaCO_3) suffered mass losses of up to 50%. Sharma et al. [221] similarly reported that bio-cemented sand retained approximately 90% of its strength and 77% of its shear modulus after 10 FT cycles. Even under favorable cementation levels, FT deterioration occurs through microcrack formation driven by pore-water expansion and freeze-induced tensile stresses. Abbasi and Hosseinpour [207] observed a 15.5% reduction in UCS after the first 2 FT cycles, followed by a plateaued degradation rate after 4 cycles. This pattern indicates that early FT cycles cause most of the microstructural disruption, with limited subsequent deterioration once primary crack networks stabilize.

The durability benefits of MICP are not restricted to granular soils. Huang et al. [206] showed that MICP-treated silty clay exhibited substantial increases in cohesion (80.9%) and internal friction angle (17.8%) relative to untreated soil after multiple FT cycles. Likewise, Yuan et al. [222] found that MICP-treated dispersive soils retained non-dispersive behavior through 20 FT cycles, outperforming their WD-cycled counterparts and confirming the relative compatibility of cohesive soils with FT exposure. Table 9 summarizes MICP-treated soil durability details under cyclic environmental loading.

The degradation rate of MICP-treated geomaterials depends not only on the occurrence of wetting–drying cycles, but also on the chemistry of the infiltrating water. In distilled water environments, deterioration is primarily driven by physical mechanisms. When water penetrates the pore system, powdery bonds, unbonded minerals, and loosely attached CaCO_3 clusters are forced into suspension and subsequently eroded. In contrast, ion-rich waters such as seawater can accelerate deterioration through salinity effects and ionic interference. This is attributed to high electrolyte concentrations that destabilize the CaCO_3 grain interface, leading to faster bond degradation and dramatically increased microcrack severity [208,212]. Water chemistry becomes even more aggressive under low-pH conditions, where acidic solutions (e.g., pH 3.5) directly dissolve the precipitated CaCO_3 bridges that provide inter-particle strength. This chemical attack consumes protons (H^+) and can result in a dramatic reduction in UCS, as the

Table 9
Quantitative summary of MICP-treated soil durability under cyclic environmental loading.

Reference	Condition (cycles)	Material (treatment)	Metric	Key finding
Liu et al. [208]	WD (1 cycle)	Sand (single treatment)	UCS loss rate	80% reduction in UCS after one WD cycle.
Abbasi and Hosseinpour [207]	FT (12 cycles)	Silty sand (0.75 M optimal)	E_{50} loss	Secant modulus declined by >50%.
Gowthaman et al. [205]	FT (25 cycles)	Slope soil (20%–23% CaCO_3)	Mass loss	Only 2% mass loss; highly durable.
Ren et al. [213]	WD and FT (9 cycles)	Poorly graded sand	UCS retention rate	WD: 34.1% vs. FT: 64.6%; WD mass loss 1.67 \times higher.
Huang et al. [206]	FT (multiple cycles)	Cohesive soil (modified)	Cohesion increase	Cohesion increased by 80.9% after FT cycling.
Rawat and Satyam [219]	WD (15 cycles)	Coastal sand + 0.40% basalt fiber	Mass loss	Minimal mass loss of 3.53% in reinforced specimens.

biogenic bridges are completely stripped away [36]. As a result, evaluating the long-term durability of MICP-treated structures requires a comprehensive consideration of pH, salinity, and dissolved ion composition to accurately predict performance under environmental cycling.

6.2.2. Large-scale tests

While laboratory investigations have established the effectiveness of MICP in enhancing soil strength, stiffness, and erosion resistance, translating these outcomes into durable, field-scale performance remains a central challenge. Long-term stability depends not only on environmental exposure but also on the spatial uniformity of CaCO_3 precipitation and the ability of treatment protocols to maintain cementation in the presence of variable hydrological and climatic processes. Accordingly, field studies emphasize three dominant considerations: (i) temporal degradation of biocemented layers, (ii) environmental mechanisms of deterioration, and (iii) the inherent heterogeneity of precipitation at larger spatial scales.

Field investigations demonstrate that MICP can rapidly stabilize near-surface soil layers, providing short- to medium-term resistance against erosion, desiccation, and liquefaction [62,163]. However, durability tends to diminish under prolonged natural exposure. Ji et al. [215] examined MICP-treated slopes subjected to 16 months of natural weathering and reported substantial losses in CaCO_3 content, with degradation ratios ranging from 63.1% to 92.1% depending on treatment scheme. These findings indicate that biocemented layers exhibit time-limited stability, and that performance strongly depends on optimizing the number of treatment cycles (typically four to six) and cementation solution concentration (e.g., 1.0 M). The progressive loss of CaCO_3 was attributed to leaching, partial dissolution, and mechanical breakdown caused by rainfall infiltration and surface runoff.

In contrast, long-term performance can be markedly superior in arid or semi-arid environments. Tao et al. [210] documented that a single MICP treatment produced a stable CaCO_3 crust that persisted for three to five years, with degradation governed predominantly by wind abrasion rather than chemical dissolution. Similarly, field trials by Liu et al. [143] on slopes exposed to natural rainfall indicated robust short- to medium-term erosion resistance. Soil loss and water infiltration were reduced by up to 87.1% and 20.8%, respectively, over an 11-month monitoring period.

A persistent obstacle to long-term durability is treatment heterogeneity in large-scale applications. Heterogeneous CaCO_3 distribution arises because cementation solutions preferentially follow existing high-permeability flow paths, reinforcing already treated zones while bypassing regions requiring cementation. As the pores clog and local hydraulic conductivity decreases, the flow is redistributed, resulting in non-uniform precipitation patterns. Terzis et al. [200] emphasized that achieving consistent and predictable large-scale performance requires addressing uncertainties associated with microbial viability, reactant transport, and the influence of soil fabric on flow partitioning. These challenges are further compounded by field-scale variability in boundary conditions, hydraulic gradients, and microbial dispersion.

Zhang et al. [61] additionally highlighted that long-term deterioration of MICP-treated materials is frequently underestimated in engineering practice. They argued that rigorous, time-dependent evaluations under severe environmental conditions—particularly those involving cyclic infiltration, salinity changes, or temperature extremes—are essential for understanding the true service life of MICP-treated systems. Collectively, these studies indicate that achieving durable, field-scale biocementation requires both improved understanding of degradation mechanisms and advancement of treatment strategies that enhance spatial uniformity, environmental robustness, and long-term mineral stability.

Field evidence from tidal environments further suggests that boundary configuration and material sequencing could be counted as two key factors, along with the intrinsic strength of the treated core, affecting the durability of MICP-treated zones. Recent field trials on Hainan Island by Li et al. [223] comparing sulfide aluminum cementing (SAC) materials and biomineralization suggest that material synergy is a necessary solution for high-energy environments, and the order of treatment strongly controls the performance. The results demonstrated that, in this layered design, applying biomineralization first to improve deeper-layer bonding, followed by a 10 cm surface layer of SAC-treated sand, created an immediate hard shell against wave impact and produced markedly better integrity than the reverse treatment sequence. Another critical analytical finding was the issue of edge scour, as the locally stiffened

Table 10

Summary of practical challenges, current status, and proposed solutions for the field implementation and upscaling of MICP technology [13,113,190,206,208,209,224–227].

Aspect	Challenges and limitations	Proposed solutions and current status
Field implementation	Severe spatial inhomogeneity of CaCO ₃ precipitation; bioclogging near injection ports restricting deep penetration; maintaining bacterial viability during injection.	Adoption of staged/two-phase injection strategies; surface percolation for shallow depths; use of temperature-controlled one-phase (TCOP) methods to delay precipitation until reagents are evenly distributed.
Long-term durability	Degradation of calcite bonds under cyclic weathering; reduction of mechanical strength and increase in mass loss over time.	MICP shows high resistance to freeze-thaw cycles but is vulnerable to severe acid rain and wet-dry cycles. Incorporating natural or synthetic fibers (e.g., jute, basalt) significantly enhances ductility and structural durability over cyclic weathering.
Environmental conditions	Sensitivity of ureolytic bacteria to extreme subsurface environments (e.g., high pressure, varying oxygen levels, low temperatures, and high salinity in marine environments).	Use of indigenous/native bacteria via biostimulation rather than bioaugmentation; isolation of extremophiles or marine strains capable of surviving in harsh, site-specific environments; encapsulation techniques for concrete applications.
Cost	High cost of analytical-grade chemical reagents (urea, calcium chloride) and laboratory-grade nutrients (yeast extract, peptone) for bacterial cultivation.	Replacement of lab-grade chemicals with industrial/agricultural by-products (e.g., corn steep liquor, lactose mother liquor, dairy waste, technical-grade reagents, or plant-based urease like jack bean extract in EICP) to substantially lower operational costs.
Scalability	Difficulty in cultivating large volumes of bacteria (>100 m ³); management of toxic ammonia (NH ₄ ⁺) by-products released during urea hydrolysis, which poses environmental and groundwater pollution risks.	Development of large-scale continuous stirred-tank reactors for field cultivation; integrating struvite precipitation to capture ammonia by-products as fertilizer; exploring alternative metabolic pathways (e.g., carbonic anhydrase, denitrification) that do not generate ammonia.

treated block created a hydraulic and mechanical contrast with the surrounding untreated sand and thereby concentrated erosion at the boundaries. This implies that future field implementations should focus on boundary transition designs rather than just the strength of the treated block.

Table 10 provides a clear, synthesized overview that outlines the practical challenges in long-term studies alongside current engineering solutions and relevant case-study insights identified in the literature.

6.3. Durability of MICP in cementitious materials and self-healing concrete

The application of MICP in cementitious materials serves two critical durability functions: (i) enhancing the intrinsic resistance of the matrix to aggressive environmental stressors, and (ii) providing autonomous, biologically driven crack healing. Assessing the long-term reliability of these functions requires evaluating not only early-age performance but also the time-dependent deterioration of both the biomineral products and the microbial agents embedded within the cementitious matrix.

6.3.1. Initial durability enhancement: densification and barrier effects

Immediately following treatment, MICP enhances durability by reducing porosity and permeability through the deposition of CaCO₃, which forms a protective barrier layer. Recent work by Zheng et al. [228] demonstrated that MICP-based surface curing for fresh concrete significantly outperforms traditional water curing. Strength improvements were considerable, and key durability metrics showed notable reductions: capillary water absorption decreased by 12.83%, electric flux by 15.50%, and the chloride ion migration coefficient by 17.36%. Fig. 14 illustrates that MICP-based surface curing consistently enhances the compressive strength of concrete compared with traditional water curing, with the degree of improvement increasing with both curing age and Ca²⁺ concentration. At all ages (3, 7, and 28 days), MICP-treated specimens exhibit higher strength. Higher Ca²⁺ availability (0.6 mol/L) yields the greatest strength gains, confirming that increased calcium concentration accelerates CaCO₃ precipitation and improves pore filling. These improvements were attributed to the formation of spherical vaterite and blocky calcite crystals, which densely coated and filled microcracks and pores, thereby restricting moisture and ion ingress.

Earlier studies further support these findings. Achal et al. [96] showed that MICP treatment reduced mortar porosity by more than 50% based on RCPT results, shifting concrete from “moderate” to “very low” permeability categories (3177 C reduced to 1019–1185 C). De Mynck et al. [75] similarly reported improvements in resistance to water, gas, and chloride penetration, as well as enhanced tolerance to freeze–thaw cycles. Collectively, these studies confirm that the primary short-term durability mechanism of MICP in cementitious materials lies in the creation of a dense, continuous biomineral layer that seals superficial defects and impedes the transport of deleterious agents.

6.3.2. Temporal healing efficacy and strength restoration trends

The autonomous crack-healing capability of MICP-treated concrete is inherently time-dependent. Laboratory investigations tracking durability indicators across multiple healing cycles reveal clear temporal recovery patterns.

Cracked mortar specimens demonstrate rapid reductions in water permeability following repeated MICP cycles. Choi et al. [91] showed that initial permeability values as high as 3.03×10^{-3} m/s decreased to 2.78×10^{-6} – 8.25×10^{-5} m/s after 7 cycles, and to

Fig. 14. Effect of Ca^{2+} concentration and curing age on compressive strength of concrete [228].

9.05×10^{-7} – 9.65×10^{-6} m/s after 21 cycles. This reduction of approximately three orders of magnitude indicates progressive infilling of crack voids by $CaCO_3$ deposits. Mechanical restoration, tracked via splitting tensile strength (STS), exhibits similar temporal trends. After 21 cycles, MICP-repaired specimens achieved STS values of 32–386 kPa, whereas specimens soaked only in water were too weak to test. Comparable results reported by Kulkarni et al. [89] (43–380 kPa after 24 cycles) confirm that $CaCO_3$ precipitates act as effective bridging agents along crack interfaces, progressively restoring load-bearing capacity.

6.3.3. Temporal deterioration: influence of crack age and matrix maturation

A major constraint on long-term MICP effectiveness is the pronounced decline in healing efficiency as concrete matures. Healing performance decreases sharply with crack age. Studies on area repair rate indicate that cracks formed at 3 days exhibited repair efficiencies of approximately 97%, whereas cracks formed at 28 days achieved only 35% [211]. Thus, microbial self-healing is most effective for very early-age cracks. This deterioration is attributed to progressive cement hydration, which reduces pore sizes (often $< 0.5 \mu m$), limiting the transport of water, nutrients, and Ca^{2+} ions. Additionally, early autogenous healing of microcracks can restrict penetration of bacterial solutions into deeper crack regions. As pore space becomes increasingly refined, both microbial activation and $CaCO_3$ precipitation are severely limited [229]. The most critical long-term durability limitation is the restricted viability of microbial agents within the alkaline cementitious environment. Unprotected bacteria remain active for only 1–2 months after concrete casting [225]. Measured viable cell concentrations decline dramatically over time, with viable counts often falling below detection limits by 135 days [211]. High pH (11–13), elevated temperatures during hydration, and reduced porosity accelerate this decline.

Encapsulation techniques include silica gel, hydrogels, polyurethane microcapsules, expanded clay, and core-shell carriers. They offer partial protection by isolating spores from the harsh matrix. Encapsulation improves durability and mechanical recovery, with polyurethane microcapsules enabling strength recovery ranging from 50% to 80%. Recent core-shell systems preserved spore viability for at least 516 days without significant morphological changes [211]. However, even with encapsulation, viability diminishes exponentially, and no existing system demonstrates bacterial survival extending to the 50-year design life of reinforced concrete structures.

Although short- and medium-term healing (months to one year) is well supported experimentally, no study to date verifies long-term microbial viability or healing capacity over multi-decade timescales. This remains a fundamental barrier to the adoption of microbial self-healing concrete in structural applications.

6.3.4. Degradation of $CaCO_3$ seals under environmental cycling

Although $CaCO_3$ is generally stable, precipitated seals are vulnerable to long-term chemical and physical degradation. Low-pH environments, such as acid rain or acidic industrial atmospheres, promote $CaCO_3$ dissolution [227]. This reduces the continuity of the mineral seal and increases permeability over time. Environmental cycles including wetting–drying and temperature fluctuations impose fatigue stresses on the $CaCO_3$ bonds. Differential expansion between the cement matrix and $CaCO_3$ crystals induces microfractures and initiates long-term deterioration (LTD). The degradation typically begins with the removal of powdery surface precipitates, followed by progressive weakening of the deeper carbonate bonds [209]. Based on the behavior of MICP-treated cementitious materials, the temporal trends were specified in Table 11.

Table 11
Temporal trends in the durability of MICP-treated cementitious materials [61,80,89,91,209,211,220,225,228,229].

Process	Time scale	Durability metric	Observation	Dominant mechanism
Healing restoration	0–21 cycles	Permeability, STS	Permeability reduced by ~3 orders of magnitude; STS restored to 32–386 kPa.	CaCO ₃ precipitation fills cracks and voids.
Strength gain cessation	7–28+ days	Compressive strength	Mineralization rate declines as concrete matures.	Reduced bacterial activity; nutrient depletion.
Viability decay (unprotected)	2–4 months	Self-healing potential	Viability limited to ≈2 months; viable cells undetectable after 135 days.	High alkalinity and pore refinement.
Healing efficiency decay	Crack age 3–28 days	Area repair rate	Repair rate drops from ~97% to ~35%.	Reduced transport due to hydration-induced pore narrowing.
Viability decay (encapsulated)	6–18 months	Self-healing potential	Core-shell systems preserve viability for 516 days; decay persists.	Encapsulation delays but does not prevent long-term viability loss.
Chemical degradation	Long-term (years–decades)	CaCO ₃ seal integrity	Dissolution under low-pH exposure; erosion in WD cycles.	Acid dissolution; fatigue of carbonate bonds.

7. Concluding remarks, limitations, and recommendations

7.1. Concluding remarks

The MICP methodology is a green and sustainable technology that is gaining prominence in geotechnical engineering for enhancing the properties of natural soil. This work presented a state-of-the-art review of the significant potential of MICP across three critical aspects, providing a new perspective for practical applications of this technology. The paper discussed the application of MICP in (i) various geomaterials, including granular soils, cohesive soils, cementitious materials, and rock; (ii) different injection methods, namely direct injection, premixing method, and percolation method; and (iii) the implementation of MICP at various scales in terms of element tests, meso-scale tests, and large-scale tests, offering insights into its effectiveness. Based on the current review, the following conclusions and promising perspectives can be drawn:

1. MICP has shown promising results in bio-cementing sands, significantly improving strength and stiffness while reducing permeability. Although the MICP process involves many variables that make strength prediction complex, it may be concluded that a minimum CaCO₃ content of 3%–4% can provide meaningful strength improvement in most cases, while CaCO₃ values exceeding 10% are generally required to achieve UCS values greater than 1000 kPa.
2. Challenges remain in treating clayey soils due to their smaller pore sizes; injection method and the spatial arrangement of CaCO₃ crystals are critical factors influencing treatment effectiveness.
3. MICP has demonstrated effectiveness in self-healing concrete cracks, improving the structural integrity of weathered rocks, and enhancing the strength and durability of concrete, thereby contributing to reduced CO₂ emissions and lower carbon footprint over time.
4. Proper selection of injection methods facilitates a more homogeneous distribution of calcium carbonate, thereby enhancing MICP efficiency. Direct injection and percolation methods are generally more suitable for coarse-grained soils, whereas the premixing method is more suited for fine-grained soils.
5. The effectiveness of MICP varies across different scales, with element tests providing detailed microstructural insights, mesoscale tests offering intermediate validation, and large-scale tests confirming real-world applicability. Although variability increases with scale due to natural conditions, large-scale applications still demonstrate substantial improvements in strength and stability.
6. MICP has shown strong potential for improving soil behavior and enhancing liquefaction resistance. Studies indicate that MICP treatment can increase liquefaction resistance by more than two times for 2.1–2.6% calcite precipitation and by 4–5 times for 3.8–7.4% calcite precipitation.

7.2. Limitations of this review

While this review aims to provide a comprehensive, cross-material, and multi-scale synthesis of MICP technology, several boundaries and omitted factors define its scope. Acknowledging these constraints is essential for accurately interpreting the comparative analyses presented:

1. This study predominantly concentrates on ureolysis-driven MICP, capitalizing on well-researched bacterial strains such as *Bacillus* and *Sporosarcina pasteurii*. Other promising bio-mediated or bio-inspired pathways, such as Enzyme-Induced Carbonate Precipitation (EICP), denitrification, sulfate reduction, or fungal-mediated precipitation, fall outside the primary scope of this analysis.

2. Although sustainability and broader environmental impacts (e.g., CCUS) are discussed, a rigorous, quantitative life cycle Assessment and a detailed economic cost–benefit analysis comparing MICP against conventional chemical stabilizers across different regional markets were not performed. The economic feasibility remains highly sensitive to local material costs and specific project scales.
3. The manuscript synthesizes mechanical, hydraulic, and durability testing outcomes but does not deeply explore the current regulatory hurdles. Furthermore, the critical lack of universally accepted testing standards tailored for bio-treated geomaterials and structural elements is not comprehensively reviewed.
4. The review evaluates long-term durability primarily from a structural and material mechanics perspective (e.g., resistance to freeze–thaw and wetting–drying cycles). The long-term ecological consequences of introducing exogenous bacteria and nutrient media along with the subsequent generation of ammonia by-products on indigenous soil microbiomes and local groundwater ecosystems are not deeply investigated.

Recognizing these limitations provides a necessary boundary for the engineering conclusions drawn in this paper and simultaneously highlights essential avenues for multidisciplinary future research.

7.3. Recommendations for future research

Following the review of current studies and envisioned applications of MICP technology, several opportunities for future research are identified:

1. Durability and environmental loading: Systematic, long-term studies are needed to quantify the behavior of MICP-derived CaCO_3 under coupled environmental actions, including wetting–drying, freeze–thaw, cyclic mechanical loading, and chemical attack (e.g., acidic or sulfate-rich environments). Particular emphasis should be placed on linking microstructural degradation (dissolution, debonding, microcracking) to macroscopic strength, stiffness, and permeability over extended timescales.
2. Multi-scale constitutive and transport modeling: Correlated chemo–hydro–bio–mechanical models are required to characterize behavioral changes in biocemented geomaterials across pore, specimen, and field scales. Such models should explicitly incorporate treatment parameters (number and timing of injections, injection mode, reactant concentrations, flow regime), microstructural evolution (pore filling, contact cementation, fabric change), and spatial heterogeneity, enabling systematic optimization of treatment protocols and prediction of long-term performance.
3. Process control and field-scale uniformity: Future work should focus on real-time monitoring and control of MICP processes in situ, for instance through distributed sensing, microfluidic-informed design, and adaptive injection strategies that respond to evolving permeability and clogging. Improving the uniformity of CaCO_3 precipitation in large volumes of soil or rock remains a central challenge for reliable design.
4. Low-carbon pathways and CCUS integration: To fully exploit the sustainability potential of bio-based cementation, further research is needed on non-ureolytic and low- CO_2 metabolic pathways, alternative carbon and nutrient sources, and the integration of MICP with carbon capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS) concepts. Quantitative life-cycle assessment and techno-economic analysis should be routinely coupled with experimental and modeling studies.
5. Advanced microbial systems and hybrid materials: There is significant scope to explore engineered microbial consortia, genetically tuned strains, and hybrid systems combining ureolytic bacteria with photosynthetic microorganisms or bio-derived polymers. Such systems could offer improved robustness, self-regulation, and multifunctionality (e.g., simultaneous mechanical reinforcement, crack healing, and carbon sequestration).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ali Zende del Nobari: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Milad Jabbarzadeh:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Numa Bertola:** Writing – review & editing. **Anupam Sengupta:** Writing – review & editing. **Arash Alimardani Lavasan:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The raw compiled datasets digitized from the literature and used to support the comparative findings of this study have been deposited in the Mendeley Data repository. The data can be publicly accessed via the following link: <https://doi.org/10.17632/35r25n6vdb.1>.

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